

A circular photograph showing a busy outdoor market stall. In the foreground, a woman with dark hair is looking at a variety of fresh produce, including tomatoes and leafy greens. An older man is also visible, looking at the goods. The background shows other market stalls and people, creating a lively atmosphere.

DELIVERABLE 1.6 GUIDELINES & TOOLS FOR REAL-LIFE INTERVENTIONS

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HISTORY OF CHANGES, January 2025

Paragraph	Page	Changed
Heading	7	Co-design numbered as section 2 instead of section 1
2	7	Link between CoP & governance event guidelines to support RLI implementation and scaling made explicit
2.3	12	Co-design while developing an RMDE unpacked
2.4	15	Power-literacy defined
2.5	20	Recognition of inclusivity considerations while using mentimeter
Heading	48	Corrected numbering of subsections
3.2	50	Irrelevant sentence about checking emails is removed
3.2	51	Sticky note comment removed
3.5	64	Section numbering corrected
4.2	66	Direct connection made between the purpose of setting up & running a CoP to strengthen and scale RLIs during the implementation phase
3.5	73	Carroll and Crawford reference completed
2 & 3	78	Direct connection made between the governance event guidelines as part of the larger set guidelines for co-creating RLIs

1. INTRODUCTION

Context: The FoodCLIC project

Europe's city-regions face significant challenges to ensure the availability and consumption of healthy, affordable, safe and sustainably produced food. Such challenges converge within local food environments, but are often neglected by public planners and policy makers. Promising initiatives taken by local governments to change the architecture of food choice often fail to become embedded in the wider policy context and to reach food-deprived and vulnerable groups.

Key factors responsible for this are: (1) siloed ways of working and (2) fragmentation of knowledge on facilitators and barriers related to food system transformation. These factors hinder the development and implementation of integrated urban food policies. **The FoodCLIC project aims to create strong science-policy-practice interfaces across eight European city-regions**, which together comprise 45 towns and cities. The backbone of such interfaces is provided by **Food Policy Networks (FPNs)**, which co-govern real-world experimental **Living Labs (LLs) of real-life interventions (RLIs)** to build a policy-relevant evidence-base through learning-in-action.

In each of the eight city-regions, an academic partner and a practice partner form a LL team. Activities in the LLs are informed by an innovative **conceptual framework (the CLIC)**, which emphasizes four desired outcomes and indicators of food system integration (sustainability co-benefits, spatial linkages, social inclusion and sectoral connectivities). Capacity-building and direct support for intensive multi-stakeholder governance (including deprived and vulnerable groups) enable policy actors and urban planners across partner city-regions to develop continuously evolving integrated urban food policies and render planning frameworks food-sensitive. Results are communicated and disseminated amongst others by extending the novel policy practices to another eight city-regions in Europe and Africa, an online Knowledge Hub, a high-level Think Tank and partners' networks. In these ways, FoodCLIC aims to contribute to **urban food environments that make healthy and sustainable food available, affordable and attractive to all citizens** (including food deprived and vulnerable groups).

RLI guideline methodology

This document contains four sets of complementary guidelines, including tools and methods. The guidelines were co-created as part of task 1.2 'Development of guidelines for policy-making, planning and co-designing and implementing of real-life interventions. The guidelines support the co-design, implementation and learning from RLIs with reflexive learning sessions (task 3.4) and a LL governance event (task 3.3). These activities are part of phase four of the FoodCLIC project: 'Designing and implementing action'. For each guideline, a kick-off event was hosted where living lab coordinators and researchers had the opportunity to decide on the contents of the guidelines, share resources and make additional requests for support that were integrated wherever possible.

The guidelines were made in a segmented sequence so that LL teams received a draft version of each guideline relevant to the approaching project phase and task responsibilities. This meant the guidelines also served as a tool for joint sense-making and adaptation to their emergent needs and anticipated capacities. Each guideline went through a round of feedback from task leaders and LL teams for a period of 2-6 weeks as well as a window of live feedback during monthly WP1 support sessions. This increased the relevance and responsiveness of the guidelines to the diverse range of city-region contexts amongst the LL teams. Furthermore, efforts were made to meet with the task leaders of a linked deliverable, such as deliverable 3.2, to ensure alignment between guidelines and template-making from the leaders of different yet inter-linked tasks.

Currently, the guidelines of 'co-design RLIs' (section 2) as well as 'implement and learn from RLIs' (section 3) have been implemented by the LL teams in the sense that they have fulfilled the guidelines' core requirements. On the rare occasion that the core requirements could not be fulfilled due to context-dependent systemic barriers and strategic priorities, the LLs informed FoodCLIC coordination (WP6) and acquired consent. A large proportion of the guideline's content contains recommended and suggested methods and tools for completing RLI activities. They were intended and used as a springboard for LLs to adapt to their own diverse and complex situations and contexts. The remaining guidelines were engaged with in a similarly adaptive way as the LLs begin RLI implementation and strategically designing their LL governance events and policymaker CoP to foster supportive policy actions that strengthen and scale the RLIs.

Structure of the guidelines & tools for RLIs

The guidelines are all structured in a similar way. Each guideline contains definitions of the key concepts or action, e.g. 'co-design', that correspond with relevant LL phases of the FoodCLIC project and the associated RLI tasks. Each guideline also contains justifications for why the action is worthwhile and co-beneficial in processes of (food) system transformation. Core requirements are also structured within each guideline as well as recommended and suggested methods and tools to adopt, adapt or not. This includes detailed facilitator scripts and resources to do co-design workshops and reflexive learning sessions. Finally, each guideline, contains links to inspiring toolkits from elsewhere, references and an appendix.

After this introduction, section 2 contains the guidelines for the co-design workshops, including selecting a RLI portfolio and progressing into RLI action plans. Section 3 contains the guidelines for implementing and learning from and adapting RLIs with a method for facilitating multi-stakeholder reflexive learning sessions. Section 4 contains the guidelines for setting up and running a Community of Practice for policymakers and Section 5 contains the guidelines for co-organizing a living lab governance event in partnership with Food Policy Networks.

2. CO-DESIGN RLIS

These guidelines intend to offer inspiration and a range of options to design fruitful and just workshops as well as spaces for the co-design of RLIs.

2.1 DEFINITIONS OF CO-DESIGN & RLIS

Co-design

In FoodCLIC, we regard co-design as an approach to design *with*, not only for, people with lived experience of current food system failures. It engages a large diversity of stakeholders working together and requires that professionals are willing to “listen, learn and, in some cases, get out of the way” (McKercher 2020). Stakeholders involved in co-design each have equal decision-making power (see figure 1, righthand) which promotes wider changes in organizational culture and governance with direct democracy. There is no co-designing without co-deciding. For more information on defining co-design, check appendix A.

Figure 1: What co-design is & is not with the position of co-design on a continuum of design approach (NEP 2023: 6-7)

Within FoodCLIC’s description of action there is an agreement for each Living Lab (LL) team to design and facilitate a **minimum of three co-design workshops** that co-generate and co-decide at least four real-life interventions that are actionable or implementable across a period of two years. Co-design workshop is a single event of at least 2 hours duration.

Real-life

interventions

Within the parameters of this FoodCLIC collaboration, and based on prior deliberations within the consortium, a working definition of a real-life intervention is:

*A **strategic combination or package of deliberate actions** that are collaboratively designed and implemented to directly and positively impact urban food environments within two years. They effectively contribute to realizing collective visions of food system transformations by acting as **leverage points** for systemic changes, e.g. the co-creation of integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning across a wider city-region scale.*

Working from this definition, a RLI contains a range of coherent actions that reflect strategies for system change. Figure 2 exemplifies six types of strategies that can be translated into actions. Actions will be diverse in nature, ranging from political to practical and from tangible to intangible. **Within every RLI a knowledge action is required to assess and evidence impact which can open access to resources and strengthen advocacy for policy change.**

Figure 2: Six types of strategies organised into pairs

There is an agreement that each LL team will co-design and implement **a minimum of four RLIs**. At least half of these will take place in the food environments of deprived areas **with communities who have relatively large proportions of people experiencing food insecurity** and/or poverty.

This does not mean all the actions of an intervention must take place within a marginalised urban neighbourhood, but it does mean the interventions aim for and work towards beneficial outcomes, e.g. more healthy and sustainable food from regional production, which reach the neighbourhood ensuring access for disadvantaged people within 2 years.

Furthermore, at least half of the interventions must contain actions that generate **inclusive and innovative business models**. Such models increase opportunities for long-term economic empowerment, healthy food access and sustainable production beyond FoodCLIC’s funding to implement RLIs for two years. Therefore, each RLI must be translated into **a provisional 2-year action plan**, organised into four action-learning cycles, **with an approximate budget** for its implementation.

It is highly recommended that the four or more RLIs of each LL also complement and strategically align. Together they cover all the CLIC pillars (see figure 3) of food system transformation and impact on at least three of the six food environments agreed upon by the consortium (agri-food; alternative-community; institutional; retail; hospitality; wild). They consider the physical and digital aspects of these food environments.

Figure 3: CLIC pillars, indicators or drivers of food system transformation

RLIs as leverage points

City-region food strategies and RLIs are sometimes referred to as leverage points with the potential to transform complex food systems. More generally, leverage points are defined as “places in a system relatively minor interventions can lead to relatively major changes” in a system’s behaviour, interconnections, trajectory and outcomes (Fischer & Riechers 2019: 116, Meadows 1999). They require enabling conditions –such as policy and planning actions – to scale-up and overcome resistance from incumbency, unequal power relations and other system barriers (Kok et al. 2021). Some of these enabling conditions we know before and some we learn by doing.

For more information on leverage points refer to Appendix A.

Two CLIC-able examples of RLIs

As requested by the living lab teams here are two examples of CLIC-able RLIs

1. *Public procurement of ecological, nutritious and regional food for free school meals*
 - Long-term contracts for regional farmers to safely transition to environmentally friendly food production, enabling business models and access low-risk loans (co-benefits, rural-urban linkages)
 - Pilot a free school meal initiative in 1-2 schools in marginalized neighbourhoods with high proportions of food insecurity (inclusion and connectivities with social welfare and health)
 - Education and training actions to prepare kitchens and staff to cook healthy school meals with more variety and seasonality
 - Knowledge action to build evidence on impact on farmer livelihoods, children's health and well-being as well as cost and knowledge sharing for application in other public canteens
 - Launch a campaign with a petition, multi-media and storytelling actions to extend the public procurement to more schools and public canteens (scale up pilot to public policy program)
 - Food environments: agri-food and institutional

2. *Multiplication & Integration of CSA farms*
 - Diverse strategic actions to access land for more CSA farms, e.g. intervention in ongoing planning processes, identification of farmers willing to share land (rural-urban linkages)
 - Innovate long-term contracts of land access for small-scale new entrant farmers to grow food sustainably with sustainable business models (co-benefits)
 - Pilot 1-2 CSAs integrating with a municipal health and wellbeing program for people with mental health and diet-related diseases. Pay for a share of the harvest to go to social and community kitchens in disadvantaged neighbourhoods (inclusion, policy connectivities).
 - Pilot peri-urban CSA farms becoming hubs for direct sales of organic produce from mid-scale rural farmers with urban citizens (rural-urban linkages, co-benefits)
 - Knowledge action to evidence impact of CSA farms on health, social cohesion, local economy, biodiversity, wellbeing etc. and advocate for policy and planning changes.
 - Food environments: agri-food, community, institutional and retail

2.2 FROM VISIONS & STRATEGIES TO CO-DESIGN

This section situates this co-design phase within a broader trajectory of a FoodCLIC collaboration. It composes of practical suggestions on how to carry forward and honour the joint-sense making and collective decisions that emerged from making **visions and strategies for systemic transformations of food environments** with stakeholders within your respected city-region context.

It will hopefully be a relief to know that you are not at the start of a co-design process and have already made a lot of progress. You have mapped the food system with stakeholders and deepened understanding of systemic problems. In response, collective visions have been made as well as

strategic themes, pathways or lines of action that will guide the actual co-design and selection of RLIs. Figure 4 charts this progress and demonstrates alignment with the double diamond design process which can be a useful visualization tool, although co-design is messier, more non-linear in practice.

Figure 4: Double Diamond design framework from the Design Council, aligned with FoodCLIC process

The visions and strategies serve as valuable democratic governance tools that build trust, accountability and ownership by demonstrating that stakeholder’s ideas were taken board and will effectively shape the co-design of real-life interventions. However, for any newcomers it is important that space remains for new ideas, changes and re-design across the course of the collaboration as well as accessible documentation of previous steps of mapping & gapping, visioning, strategizing and co-design.

Practically, you can use the co-generated vision drawings and statements in your co-design workshops. Furthermore, your collective strategy contains at least four strategic pathways, themes or lines of action (recorded in template 3.1) that can structure your co-design sessions and guide towards four RLIs. Figure 5 visualises which components of your city-region food system (CRFS) strategy can serve as criteria to co-design and select RLIs. Section 5 of the guidelines contains more information on a practical method to democratize the selection of RLIs with the use of minimum criteria, feasibility check, collaboration sign-up and vote of support.

Figure 5: CRFS strategy components (2-4) become RLI criteria for design and selection

2.3 CO-DESIGN WHILE DEVELOPING A REFLEXIVE MONITORING AND DYNAMIC EVALUATION (RMDE) FRAMEWORK

As important as carrying forward collective work from the past into the RLI co-design workshops is bridging to future events. After the co-design workshops, there will be four multi-stakeholder events with 5 to 6-month intervals during a two-year period of implementing action. These events are linked to FoodCLIC’s description of action as “plan-action-observation-reflection-re-planning cycles” with the first cycle starting in May and ending with a “multi-stakeholder reflexive learning session” in September/October 2024. They aim to facilitate an “action-learning spiral” where interventions can be **adapted during implementation** to respond to systemic barriers, enhance co-benefits and build evidence for making integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning.

It is worthwhile envisioning that many of the stakeholders who participate in the co-design of RLIs will also participate in its implementation, reflexive monitoring and dynamic evaluation (RMDE) with differentiated roles, responsibilities and benefits. An RMDE is a framework where what gets evaluated can change (dynamic) and the monitoring approach is guided reflections. Although there will be core indicators that enable comparative baseline and end-line assessments and learning across all LLs, there is also a need to localise a RMDE process to each city-region context. The co-design workshops present an invaluable opportunity to promote clarity, transparency and mutual accountability on the allocation of public funds to realize systemic interventions. This means being explicit on changes (i.e. objectives) that each action of a RLI aims to achieve with indicators of success that are valuable for the participants and can be evidenced without (over)burdening.

A general RMDE framework has been co-created and further training on how to develop a local RMDE framework took place. However, there are things worth considering early in the co-design process. Here are some tips/requirements to include in your co-design process:

1. What are the objectives specific to your city-region?

The objectives that are considered important to your city-region probably belong to different themes, e.g., sustainability, health/nutrition, but also governance and/or learning. It may be good to make a distinction between objectives related to outcomes and to processes that facilitate food system transformation.

2. How does the proposed intervention aim to create change towards the set objective and how can you tell that you have moved in that direction?

Based on the objectives, we suggest that you have a first discussion on indicators that provide insight into the aspired change. A couple of things are important in the selection of these indicators. First, it is important to consider process indicators, i.e. quality of collaboration, and outcome indicators, i.e. final impact. Second, be mindful that indicators are sensitive to change, so that it is possible to evaluate progress on them during the six-monthly cycles. Third, indicators should be able to capture a diverse set of outcomes. How can you, for example, monitor progress in learning, or in increased sensitization to food system topics with policymakers? For these aspects, reflexive monitoring tools, such as a DLA, may be helpful. Fourth, as part of the participatory aspects, it may be relevant to incorporate a technique such as 'most significant change', to reflexively monitor how interventions contributed to change as experienced by participants, bystanders and policymakers.

3. How can the indicators aid in the transformation process, by becoming meaningful measures?

Indicators tend to cause actions to become distracted from the initial goal. In addition, monitoring and evaluation can be burdening. For these reasons, it is important to consider for all indicators who is burdened by the data collection, as well as who actually benefits. Monitoring FoodCLIC, city-region and intervention specific goals requires you to keep track of the monitoring needs at these different levels. In addition, we encourage you to think how the collection of information can empower the transformation process, as opposed to distract it. You can do so, by specifying for each indicator who benefits from the data collected.

The making of more details for the learning and action plan of each RLI (required as an output of your final co-design sessions but not for the RLI portfolio and D3.2) can act as a valuable tool to localize your RMDE framework and organise the following reflexive learning sessions. Below is a set of questions to stimulate thinking and linking towards what happens after the co-design workshops. How may you facilitate collaborative and adaptive governance while implementing RLIs?

- When we did action(s)... we aimed for change(s)... evidenced by the success indicators of...
- Did the change(s) happen and why or why not? Link to observations and reflections on actions.
- Where there any unintended positive or negative effects? What can we learn from them?
- What, if any adaptations, do we make for our next actions to achieve change(s) ___?
- How was it to work and make decisions together, how can we improve our collaboration?
- Who else should co-benefit and be involved in this intervention group?
- What learning/knowledge is still needed for the next cycle?

2.4 ASSEMBLING CO-DESIGN TEAMS & CREATING SAFE SPACES

Co-design sensitively works across differences in power, perspective and identity to create positive change. It encourages us to design with those “closest to the pain and furthest from power” (Pressley 2018) because those who experience oppressive pains of our food systems, such as food insecurity and precarious land access, “hold unique perspectives on how these systems need to change” (NEP 2023).

The following section focuses on the who and where of co-design by encouraging the assembly of mixed co-design teams in safe spaces with transformative potential. It is majorly sourced from KA McKercher’s extensive experience distilled in their book ‘beyond sticky notes: doing co-design for real’ (2020).

Assembling co-design teams

It is recommended that **for each RLI there is a co-design team with a limit of 12 people** to prioritise trust, intimacy and social connection. Small circles tend to be less intimidating and easier to share power and care for each other. A co-design team is more likely to be transformative when there is a mix of people with lived experience, professionals working with and/or for people with lived experience and provocateurs (McKercher 2020).

1. People with lived experience:

Are people with **first-hand experience** of a systemic problem, failure or injustice, such as food insecurity and social exclusion from being undocumented people or precarious land access from being small-scale agroecological farmers. They may also be leaders of disadvantaged communities and spokespeople from marginalised neighbourhoods who draw on their own experience and are interested in being part of a team, sharing thoughts, learning and taking action.

To support power sharing, recruit more people with lived experience than professionals. When recruiting community leaders, it is better to ask a range of people for nominations than relying on a few individuals who self-assign themselves as leaders. It is vital to compensate these participants for their contributions (see section 2.7 for more information) to recognise their invaluable work as co-designers and ensure long-term participation.

2. Professionals working with and/or for people with lived experience:

Co-design teams benefit from a diversity of professionals from different perspectives, backgrounds and identities. It is critical that they don't come to 'fix' marginalised people. Moreover, at least some of the professionals should be '**influencers**', i.e. people who are direct decision-makers with power to create changes in organisations and systems. In the case of FoodCLIC they would likely be institutional leaders, policy makers, politicians, and planners. "Involving influencers in co-design has ripple effects as they take new knowledge and ways of working back into their contexts" (McKercher 2020).

If you're concerned that they might behave inappropriately, speak with them beforehand and share some tips on power-sharing and appropriate mindsets for co-design (see section 6). Also be careful not to invite academics who cannot learn and share because they are stuck in lecturing mode and dominate discussions with their single solution.

3. Provocateurs:

Provocateurs neither have first-hand experience nor do they have professional expertise in relation to food system change. In a way they are outsiders who do not come with a solution in mind, but may bring examples from other spaces, e.g. in energy and housing systems. They act as a buffer to challenge power differentials by encouraging professionals to be clear and challenge assumptions.

Above all they must be curious, prefer consent-driven language (see section 5) and have some power literacy, i.e. understand and analyse power dynamics such as inequalities in terms of representation and decision-making. It can be useful to share a provocateur role description when assembling co-design teams and to choose people from your own networks of trusted friends and colleagues.

Support team

The support team guide and care for the people participating in co-design. They include the roles of convener/facilitator, design coach, coordinator, caretaker and community connector (McKercher 2020). One person cannot play all support roles, and it is highly recommended that at least one community partner from each participating neighbourhood becomes part of the support team. They can choose to take on some of these roles and substantially increase the likelihood that people with lived experience will attend, access and feel safe in the workshops. It is also recommended to have an artist in the support team who can stimulate creativity and make complex information accessible, interesting and *affective*.

It may be that one neighbourhood may already be united with a community organisation that may want to co-organise, host and facilitate co-design sessions while supporting a co-design team. This work would need to be fairly remunerated, which is possible within the WP3 budget (see section 9). It might feel strange or risky at first to step aside and make space for distributed leadership of an RLI. What's key is agreement on a fair and inclusive approach to co-design that democratically choose RLIs based on common selection criteria (section 5) and that the RLI reaches an implementable state of design, e.g. action plan with estimated budget.

A model of care for creating safe co-design spaces

"We can't figure out how to create safety as we go along. We need to figure it out before we start" (McKercher 2020: 89). Ensuring safe conditions for intercultural exchange and participation of people with lived experience of systemic marginalisation requires more care and hospitality from a support team. Safety is made through careful words and actions, by giving options, validating people's experiences and practicing consent-driven language. It is about slowing down and checking-in to prioritise relations. "If you don't have time to build relations, you don't have time to co-design (ibid: 91). Below is a summary of McKersher's *Model of Care for Co-design* that you can adapt to your context.

Table 1: Adapted summary of McKersher's Model of Care for Co-design (2020)

Before bringing co-design teams together	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the fit (are you the right person for the work? Is co-design needed and will it increase people's power and dignity?) • Establish a support team • Build relationships (e.g. phone calls, cook and eat together, listen to past experiences and identify strengths) • Offer genuine invitations (clear in ask and offer with choices in how to take part and a person touch that appreciates strengths) • Widen inclusion (see figure 6)
Keep the teams together	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect co-designers (warm welcome, define and maintain boundaries, space for storytelling, valuing strengths & resilience) • Seek ongoing feedback (ask how people feel, how do you know people feel safe, is something hopeful being created together?) • Have courageous conversations (address harmful actions with compassion, prioritise safety above comfort of privileged people) • Care for each other (peer support, schedule and hold time for pre-brief and de-brief, do not take on too many initiatives in one time)
Working safely within your support team and with co-designers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serious disclosure (connect people to appropriate support and follow-up, make a mandatory notification) • Safe disclosure (support people to share stories safely, learn from people who run peer support groups) • Rights and responsibilities for co-designers (see figure 6 for example to adapt with co-designers)

- **Agreements for recognition, attribution and payment** (pay participants with lived experience expertise, see section 9)

Figure 6 offers some practical ideas from McKersher’s (2020: 107 & 123) book on how to widen inclusion and affirm many people’s identities (as they define them) as well as an example proposal for the rights and responsibilities between co-designers and the support team.

Ten principles for widening inclusion

1. **Remove barriers**
Pre-empt barriers to participation and remove them.
2. **Slow down**
Give people time to connect, think and learn.
3. **Go beyond writing**
Embrace visual (see page 133), oral and somatic practices.
4. **Support power-sharing**
Encourage people to use their names, not titles (page 157, 160).
5. **Practise flexibility**
Remain open to how people can and want to participate.
6. **Seek consent**
Apply consent-driven convening (see page 131).
7. **Use affirming language**
Focus on strengths and dignity.
8. **Be mindful of sensory differences**
Remain aware of sensory load and sensory differences.
9. **Ensure safe venues**
Ensure that venues are accessible, neutral and comfortable.
10. **Seek intersectionality**
Seek co-designers who can speak across many identities.

We're in this together. We give no special privileges to people with letters before or after their name (e.g. 'Dr' or 'PhD') or with more income, education or wellness. All backgrounds are equal. We use each other's first names and refer to each other as people – not by titles, acronyms or slang. There is no such thing as 'just' having lived experience.

You are welcome here. We respect your identity and will work to ensure other co-designers do too. If someone challenges or disrespects your identity or experience, we will support you, regardless of their intentions. We'll use and respect your pronouns and your preferred name.

You can choose what you're comfortable with sharing. We won't ask you to disclose anything personal. If you do, we'll listen with compassion, believe your experience and agree not to be judgemental through our words or body language. In return, you need to do the same for others.

You help to make this space safe. We need your help to make this space safe for everyone. This requires us all to be kind, curious and hospitable, and to defer judgement in favour of understanding. We are tough on systems and gentle with individuals. The organisers will step in when the space is unsafe; please tell us in real time if we don't notice.

You can ask, and we will ask too. We want to know about anything that helps you to be included and to stay included – for example, bringing a support person, delaying decision-making or changing your small group. We will regularly ask you for feedback on your experience, and we want your honest thoughts. There will never be repercussions or unfriendliness from the organisers if you tell us we didn't do a good job. If you do, we will try to improve. If we can't, we'll try to find someone better suited.

You don't have to ask for permission to do things such as go to the bathroom or take time out. *Co-design isn't school.*

Figure 6: Practical principles to widen inclusion (left) with example of rights & responsibilities (right)

Co-creative places

Careful selection of the venues or physical places of co-design can also promote safety and confidence to be creative and transform power relations. Prioritise accessibility and comfort for people with lived experience and avoid assuming by asking for feedback before booking a venue. Consider places with lots of light with additional rooms for people to rest as well as nearby green space for walks and energiser activities. Where possible hire catering services and rent venues in the neighbourhoods you are co-designing with. Same applies if a RLI co-design team emerges to support precarious small-scale farmers then try to co-host a session in a participating farm.

Equitable participation

Far more effective than design tools, is the practice and building of appropriate mindsets (ways of thinking and doing) for co-design to enable equitable participation. McKarther identifies six mindsets for co-design which are briefly summarised below and can be read in more detail [here](#).

1. **Elevating lived experience** – generously listen, take seriously, work from strengths, encourage self-representation, and support with robust action
2. **Being in the grey** – willingness to be uncomfortable, unclear and confused, befriend uncertainty and resist quick fixes
3. **Valuing many perspectives** – see old issues in new ways, maintain a systems perspective, uncover values and attitudes, changing systems is a relational process
4. **Curiosity** – defer judgement to deepen understanding, ask quality questions, use humility, learn and form insight with support structure for learning, play and peer support
5. **Hospitality** – make time for care and connection, build trust, create a welcoming, safe and comfortable setting, prioritize people with lived experience of system failures,
6. **Learning through Doing** – test before fully implementing, experiment and prototype, explore new ways to collaborate and take decision, set personal preferences aside, take safe risks

If you are concerned that some of participants in the co-design workshops may not be willing to share space and power, then it is recommended to make these mindsets for co-design explicit from the start and to build activities into the workshops that enable and reward the practice of these mindsets (see section 2.6 for examples). Sharing power is not about being quiet and passive, but wanting to listen, learn and be able to make changes together.

A pro-active approach is recommended by making and sending a **welcoming co-design brief** before the workshops that shares information and prepares the co-designers for fruitful engagement. The brief should be short and visually attractive. It's recommended to include the 6 mindsets for co-design, a draft of rights and responsibilities of co-designers (see Figure 6), an introduction of co-design process with RLI selection criteria (see Table 2), a minimal summary of vision and strategy as well as practical event details. If you sense people cannot access the information digitally, visit them in person.

Facilitation recommendations for equitable participation

- Small tables of up to 5-6 participants with a mix of people with lived experience, professionals and provocateurs. Avoid tokenism and minoritising by arranging tables with a majority of people with lived experience.
- Sensitizing activities and reminders built into the workshops with invitations to recognise privileges and promote self-regulation of how much you speak in relation to others
- Pass around an object in a circle or round to ensure everyone has an opportunity to speak
- Make space for silence for people to generate their own ideas and set a limit on how many post-it/sticky notes for each person, refer to post-it notes from people with lived experience if they are shy to speak
- **Call in:** if someone uses harmful language, call in the group to respond by asking a question, e.g. "how might the language be harmful? What would be a kind way of communicating what was said?"
- **Call out:** if someone is dominating or being harmful, speak up and share your observation publicly. Once safe, continue the activity. "Prioritise the safety of marginalised people above the comfort of privileged people" (McKarter 2020: 113).
- Make space to recognise and value the strengths, aspirations, culture and resistance of people with lived experience, instead of only focusing on their experience of system failures
- Apply consent-based decision making and where possible offer options for participation
- Avoid long-periods of abstract and technical information sharing (e.g. above 10 minutes), and make sure to have plenty of rests, energizers and playful embodied activities.

Whereas facilitation is about making things easier, convening is the art of inviting participants to gather and co-create great outcomes together. Convening prioritises the building mutual trust and respect which are key ingredients for sustaining engaged collaborations. For more information on the principles and indicators of **transformational convening** and how it contrasts to transactional convening, refer to Appendix B.

Intercultural and intergenerational co-design

It is highly likely that the co-design team will compose of people from different cultures, generations and socio-economic groups. In many of the participating neighbourhoods, there is a history of systemic marginalisation and exclusion from the dominant societal group. It is not a coincidence that food insecurity is disproportionately experienced by people who face compound oppression by not belonging to a majority group or dominant culture (e.g. profession, gender, ethnicity and/or sexuality) nor having inherited privilege (e.g. being born into a middle-class family). It is currently beyond the scope of WP1 to give sufficient guidance based on our own limited positions and privileges. Therefore, we have requested for external support with two facilitated learning sessions to accompany these guidelines.

2.5 DECISION-MAKING METHODS & TOOLS

This section is dedicated to decision-making methods and tools that revolve around working with selection criteria and context-appropriate applications of consent and voting.

Working with selection criteria to co-decide RLI portfolio

Section 2 of the guidelines and the strategic planning training encourages you to be fair and transparent on the making and taking of decisions by **co-generating RLI design & selection criteria**. A method is offered as a democratic, principled and pragmatic way of deciding which of the co-designed RLIs will be chosen for implementation.

The recommendation is to prepare and send workshop participants a ‘**co-design brief**’ that gives a short orientation and clearly states the minimum criteria for a RLI to be selected to enter a final decision round. This final decision round consists of three equally weighted components: a feasibility check, a collaboration sign-up and a vote of support within an accessible time period (deadline for submitting RLI portfolio, D3.2).

Mentimeter activity to add local selection criteria:

If you were unable to co-generate criteria for RLI selection in your strategizing workshop, it can be remedied near the beginning of your first co-design workshop. You can share the recommended criteria shown in the left column of table 2 which are based on foodCLIC’s description of action. Then ask participants to generate additional criteria with mentimeter voting of two rounds. Please, note that mentimeter may not be accessible to every participant, so consider bringing devices and assistance so everyone can vote. A first round where everyone can propose one additional criterion, and a second round where everyone can select three criteria from the first round. The four most popular criteria can be added to the selection criteria in Box 6 of table 2.

Table 2: Seven core criteria for co-design and selecting RLIs

Criteria from EU-FoodCLIC DoA agreement	Criteria from city-region collaboration
1. Connects and positively impacts at least two food environments within 2 years (agri-food; community; institutional; hospitality; retail; wild)	2. Directly contributes to the collective vision of at least two food environments (generated in previous workshop)
3. Increases access to healthy sustainable food for people experiencing food insecurity AND/OR involves business model(s) for long-term production/access to healthy sustainable food	4. Directly contributes to at least one of the 4+ strategic themes, objectives or lines of action (generated in previous workshops)
5. Applies at least three of CLIC’s pillars of system transformation (co-benefits; rural-urban	6. Applies at least two additional/local criteria for selecting RLIs (co-generated

linkages; social inclusion; connectivities with other systems and policy priorities)	with collaborators, e.g. in strategy workshop or mentimeter activity, page 13).
7. Offers possibilities for meaningful connections and cooperation with other proposed RLIs	

You may choose to add a point scoring system where designs that incorporate more criterion, food environments, CLIC pillars, etc. gain more points. Therefore, the designs with most points are selected. But, perhaps as important as content and principle criteria are the feasibility of the RLI, the sense of collectively ownership and political buy-in. The method proposes integrates these considerations by adding a ‘sign-up call’ to join the prospective RLI co-design team in next second workshop and a vote of support that can be done online within a stated time to enable more people to be part of the process.

The ‘feasibility check’ can be as simple as assessing whether it can be at least pilotable (partially implemented) with 25,000 euro (approx. 25% of implementation budget) with measurable impact on food environments within two years. The ‘collaboration sign-up’ indicates whether a minimum of 5 stakeholders are willing to collaborate in the co-design team and ‘vote of support’ enables a democratic selection if there are more than four RLI design proposals that meet all the selection criteria. Figure 7 serves as a visual aid to summarise this suggested decision-making method for co-deciding the RLI portfolio.

Figure 7: Summary of decision-making method for selecting RLI portfolio

See section 2.6, workshop A, for more support on how to practically integrate this method into your first co-design workshop. To ensure a balance in neighbourhood-centred and city-region scale interventions you can make three voting blocs/streams, i.e. a voting for RLIs in neighbourhood X, for neighbourhood Y and for city-region scale. You could also make voting streams for particular strategic lines of actions or combinations/pairings of them.

From voting to consent

You have hopefully become more confident with the use of sticker 'dotmocracy' and mentimeter as tools for voting and prioritising. Usually voting works well in contexts with larger groups above 15 people. It is recommended in the first co-design workshop to stay with voting to effectively select a RLI portfolio. Application of consent-based decision making is recommended in the following co-design workshops, once RLIs are selected, and smaller co-design (and implementation) teams assemble with a recommended limit of 12 people per team.

It is a rare event where everyone in a mixed team agrees on the best decision for everybody (consensus), but it is common for small groups to reach a shared place of acceptance or tolerance (consent) around a decision. Consent is an effective way to share power, making space for meaningful participation of everyone in 'good enough' decisions to forward and experiment together.

With consent-based decision-making people must give a 'reasoned' no (an objection) to a proposal. Then a dialogue follows to adapt the proposal until there are no objections and consent is found or to simply drop the proposal and potentially re-propose at another time. A much clearer and practical explanation of how to facilitate consent when proposals are made in small teams or circles is available by clicking on the figure 8 below. There is also an activity (round 2, page 25) within the 2nd co-design workshop in section 6 where co-design teams practice consent when proposing different parts of the action plan and budget.

Figure 8: [consent decision-making method](#) by Sociocracy For All

Although it may seem like a loss of time to co-develop decision-making, it is actually a great investment that will make it easier to move forward when teams get stuck in the future and objections arise. FoodCLIC is an opportunity to innovate governance with space to learn by doing

and also space to fail safely, adapt and try again. Confrontation and conflict are part of co-design as well as transformation. There is no 'one' right way to co-design and these guidelines are not meant as instructions to dictate your practice.

2.6 AN ADAPTABLE 2-PART CO-DESIGN SEQUENCE

This section offers a series of two co-design workshops of approximately 3 hours as a starting point or adaptable material for realizing your own workshops.

Workshop A is designed to strategically co-generate and democratically decide which real-life interventions will become part of a RLI portfolio and resourced into implementation. It is structured so that RLIs are co-designed around all four of the strategic lines of actions or pathways. It ensures at least one RLI is selected with/for each of the two collaborating neighbourhoods and at least two RLIs concentrate on the city-region scale.

Workshop B focuses on making RLIs in the portfolio actionable with a co-design team for each intervention. Some activities and methods are offered to encourage multi-stakeholder collaboration agreements by co-designing an action plan with clear roles and responsibilities and a budget for implementation.

Adaptable combinations of co-design workshops

The suggested sequence of two workshops is designed to be flexible so you can combine them in different ways to align with your contexts and capacities. For example, workshop A can be a very large 1st workshop with all the potential co-designers (e.g. 48 people) from the neighbourhoods and city-region scale, while workshop B can then be repeated in each of the collaborating neighbourhoods with two parallel co-design teams, one working on neighbourhood-centred RLI from the portfolio, the other on a complementary city-region RLI (sharing the same event venue with their own tables). Alternatively, you can repeat workshop A twice in both neighbourhoods, but with a different pairing of strategic lines of actions around which participants co-design RLI proposals. Then also repeating workshop B twice with same or different pairings of parallel co-design teams. Pairing co-design teams generates opportunities for different RLIs to strategically align or cross-pollinate. These workshop combinations are visualised in figure 9. There are many more possible combinations such as grouping neighbourhood-centred RLIs in workshops instead of pairing with city-region RLIs.

<p>Workshop A</p> <p>Co-design groups form and propose around all 4 strategic lines of actions/pathways</p> <p>2 strategic lines clearly dedicated to food insecure & marginalised neighbourhoods</p>	<p>Workshop B</p> <p>2 parallel co-design teams Neighbourhood RLI 1 City-region RLI 1</p> <p>Workshop B</p> <p>2 parallel co-design teams Neighbourhood RLI 1 City-region RLI 1</p>	<p>Workshop A</p> <p>Neighbourhood strategic pathway 1 City-region strategic pathway 1</p> <p>Workshop A</p> <p>Neighbourhood strategic pathway 2 City-region strategic pathway 2</p>	<p>Workshop B</p> <p>2 parallel co-design teams Neighbourhood RLI 1 City-region RLI 1</p> <p>Workshop B</p> <p>2 parallel co-design teams Neighbourhood RLI 2 City-region RLI 2</p>
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Figure 9: Possible workshop combinations

You may realize there are evident needs, sufficient time and budget for the realization of more than 3 workshops to ensure the building of trust, new partnerships and genuine collective decision making. This is especially recommended if you feel rushed, ethically compromised and at risk of falling into ‘transactional convening’ (see Appendix B).

Workshop A: ‘From ideas to a co-decided RLI portfolio’

Preparation

Confirm booking of a co-creative place and catering as early as possible. Ensure there is plenty of space between tables, limited to 6 people per table for quality participation. If you want to do workshop A once and generate all the RLI proposals, a larger space is required with capacity for 8 tables to generate at least 8 RLI proposals with a maximum of 48 participants, including at least 4 facilitators. If you want to do workshop A twice, e.g. one for neighbourhood-centred RLIs and one for city-region scale RLIs, then 4 tables is sufficient meaning a maximum of 24 participants.

A **co-design brief** is prepared and communicated to participants before the co-design workshop with a link to sign-up which requires stating their preferences on co-designing interventions in (1) which food environments, and (2) on which scale (a concrete neighbourhood or city-region scale). Prepare a PowerPoint presentation that re-communicates the co-design brief and workshop activities with as few words as possible. Prepare the tables with stationery, hospitality card (see activity 2), people’s name cards for a careful and strategic mix of stakeholders. For example, to ensure some RLI proposals centre on neighbourhood 1 & 2, ensure to name the tables and invite participants who are from the neighbourhoods and/or expressed preference for this scale of design. You can also organise tables and matchmake participants around pairs of food environments.

Figure 10: Visual aid for table organisation, a max of 6 people per table

Workshop Activity Sequence

1. Opening (15 minutes max):

Start with a lot of gratitude and an attractive presentation of today's co-design brief (including mindsets for co-design) that reminds of the prior process, vision and strategy (1 slide each), and also gives oversight of what comes next: selection of RLI portfolio, assembly of co-design and implementation teams in workshop B followed by four cycles action and learning with four reflexive learning sessions.

Inform the participants of the matchmaking logic of the tables (preferred scale and/or food environments) and the overall aim of today is to build relations and learn from each other. This enables the making of collective proposals for RLIs using a common template (figure 11) to meet minimum selection criteria. Explain your RLI selection method clearly with using a visual aid (e.g. figure 7).

2. Warm-up activity (15 minutes):

Remind the participants that co-design is not only about tools, but also about mindsets, believing that everyone is creative and that lived experience is as valuable as professional knowledge. Two key mindsets for co-design are hospitality and curiosity which enable trust, care, learning and building of new partnerships and hopefully even new friendships.

Show figure 11 as a Powerpoint slide that describes this warm-up activity which is also printed and placed on each table as a 'hospitality card'. Stress the importance of first meeting each other as people, listening to who we are, why each of us is here personally, with an invitation to **not** mention anything about our work, professions, initiatives, i.e. what we do.

Four Dimensions of Hospitality

McKercher (2020: 67)

Warm-up activity:

Get to know the people on your table

Pair up with somebody on your table and try to know each other as people. Don't mention about your work, profession or initiatives.
Focus on who you are, not what you do.

1. Ask these questions to each other and listen with generosity.
 - 1) What is your favourite breakfast and why?
 - 2) What brings you here personally?
 - 3) What is one quality or thing you appreciate when working in teams?
2. After 10 minutes, share with the rest of the table, 1 thing you learnt and appreciate about the person you listened to.

Figure 11: Hospitality card and activity description for warm-up activity.

3. First round: strategy focus & motivating actions (30-45 minutes)

Remind the participants that interventions are different to individual initiatives because they combine actions/activities from multiple initiatives for strategic effect. Interventions are about experimenting and learning together by combining our own strengths and resources for system change.

The first round of co-design is about each table choosing a strategic focus with dotmocracy, i.e. agreeing on which two strategic pathways or lines of action etc. they will design towards, supported by **self-generated action proposals** that each person feels most motivated to do. With some good fortune and respectful communication, they may be able to combine actions and already seed 1-2 RLIs that will be further strengthened in the second round after the break. Make use of figure 12 to communicate the hopeful outcome of the first round.

Figure 12: Visual aid, representing a table proposing actions and hopefully combining into an RLI

Facilitators ensure each table has an attractive A3 1-page summary of strategy workshop(s) on each table (4-5 strategic objectives, themes, line of actions, OR pathways etc. is an accessible maximum with 4-5 sentences of information in total) and give each participant two dot stickers. Invite the participants to place the stickers onto two strategies, on the A3 page, they would like to contribute to with an RLI. Look at the results of the sticker voting, ask the members if they are willing to focus on proposing actions that contribute to the two most voted/valued strategies (can of course extend to three if it's very close). Write them down as the table's strategic focus and celebrate the first decision being made together.

Facilitators give each person a hexagon card and ask them to write down their name and 1 action or activity that they would really like to happen and also see contributing to the table's strategic focus. An action they feel motivated to actually do in the future. In a round one by one, each participant describes their action and explains how it contributes to a part of the table's strategic focus.

The round finishes with participants proposing to join their actions (hexagons) together to make 1-2 RLI proposals on each table. Extra actions (hexagon cards) can be added when two or more people are willing to support the action and agree that it strengthens other actions on the table. Ask the table to give a name to their potential 'RLI seed' and to make it easy for other tables to read them and give feedback after the break. If any person's action cannot be combined or they don't feel so connected to the table, you can inform them that they can request a table swap after the break.

4. Break, feedforward and table swaps (30 minutes)

Invite the participants to rest, stay hydrated, enjoy a snack, and make use of the restrooms if they haven't already. Encourage them to take a look at the RLI seeds of other tables. If they have any feedback, such as ideas or concerns, they can write them on post-it notes and place them on the tables next to, but not on top of, the hexagons. If any participant is feeling more attracted or motivated to contribute to a different table for the second round, they can request a table swap as long as there aren't more than 6 people on a co-design table.

5. Energiser (15 minutes)

Invite everyone to form a circle and to do a short energizer activity to support digestion and flow of creative juices! In a round, each person suggests a stretch or movement that everyone can copy. If a big group, keep an eye on the time, maybe it's not possible to do a full round. Also clarify it's fine if anyone doesn't feel like doing a stretch.

6. Second round: Co-designing a selectable RLI proposal (45 minutes)

Remind the co-designers that the remaining time is dedicated to transforming their RLI seeds into RLI proposal. Proposals that meet the minimum selection criteria and therefore be chosen to become part of RLI portfolio and move into co-design workshop B and implementation. It is worth reminding the participants of your decision-making method for selecting RLIs (e.g. figure 7). It's probably not realistic to select in the workshop but more inclusive and fairer to digitalise the proposals and open them up for online voting, collaboration sign-ups for a stated period. Also, it's worth stating how many interventions you have capacity to coordinate, support and administer (e.g. 4-5).

RLI PROPOSAL TEMPLATE			
What's the name of your RLI and its main objectives?	Who feels ownership in this RLI and what are the shared responsibilities?	Which 2+ CLIC pillars does it contribute to and how?	Which local criteria does it contribute to and how?
Name: Team members: Objectives: (2 outcomes, 1 process) 1. 2. 3. <small>(outcomes = what you want to achieve, process = how you want to work together)</small>	 Who else is welcome to join your co-design team if selected (12 people max per team)?		
How does your RLI contribute to the collective vision of 2+ food environments?	Which strategic line of actions or objectives does it contribute to & how?	What are the main actions or activities in 1 st & 2 nd year?	What will you observe if your actions are successful?
		Year 1 Year 2	

Figure 13: RLI proposal template for 2nd round corresponding with D3.2 template

Inform the participants that every table is invited to use the same RLI proposal template (figure 13) to support them to meet the minimum selection criteria and to make it easier for everyone to understand each other's RLI proposals for the closing activity (and when they go online for voting and collaboration sign-up). They are also very much encouraged to add creative communication, such as audio and visual components that can be part of their proposal, e.g. drawings, diagrams, symbols, a video etc. Inform the participants that each table has x2 A2 RLI proposal template (in case two RLIs emerged from 1 table) as well as 2-3 copies of the printouts that provide support on meeting minimum selection criteria (1-page vision, 1-page strategy, 1-page FoodCLIC pillars, 1-page local criteria, etc.).

Facilitators give each person three sticky notes to start with and ask everyone to first think personally for themselves, to read the question boxes on the template and come up with their own answers for

three questions. They write down the answers on the sticky notes and stick them onto the relevant question box. This individual work (approx. 5 minutes) is accompanied by some calm acoustic music (without lyrics) to aid concentration and encourage 'silent work'.

The rest of the time (35 minutes) is dedicated to completing the template independently as a group as well as adding creative communication. Recommend that they go box by box and check that everyone agrees before (re)moving sticky-notes and writing the answers in pen. Agreeing on specific objectives of their proposed RLI will make it easier to answer the other questions. It may make sense for them to merge sticky-notes that are very similar and add new ones etc. Remind them that facilitators are present if they want any clarification or support. Make sure to give some gentle reminders of how much time is remaining. 5 minutes before the end of the activity ask the groups to complete the template and to stick it onto the wall so that other groups can read their proposals for the closing activity. Make sure they include their names on the template.

7. Closing activity (15 minutes)

Figure 14: Visual aid using sticky notes & template for feedback poster

Thank the participants for their amazing engagement, their willingness to listen to each, be curious, collaborate and make collective proposals together. As a closing you invite them to read each other's proposals as a kind of walking gallery. With green coloured sticky-notes they communicate if they want to actively be part of co-design and implementation team of this RLI proposal and share 1 thing they really like about it. With the orange notes they can write down any concern or suggestion they have for any of the RLI proposals. Also invite them to give feedback on the workshop and the overall co-design process looking to the future by adding sticky-notes onto the feedback poster on the wall (see figure 14). Thank participants again, remind them how you will follow-up (digitalise, share online for voting and collaboration sign-up, etc.) and welcome them to food and refreshments.

In-between: Selecting RLIs & Re-assembling Co-design teams

Check whether the RLI proposals meet all the minimum criteria and pass a basic feasibility check. Send a kind communication to those that did not meet these criteria and explain why. Digitalise the RLI proposals that did meet the criteria. Consider if it's necessary to add all 8 of the answers from the template (figure 13). Try to find a balance so its accessible enough for people to read all the proposals and enough information to make informed decisions (perhaps name, objectives and actions is enough with a link to a photograph of the template for more information?)

Send out a follow up e-mail (also to people who did not or could not participate) with the proposals and make a request for people to send an e-mail back to you that communicates which proposals they support/vote for (e.g. I support proposals 2, 6, 7 etc.) and which proposal(s) they feel motivated to further co-design and implement (I feel motivated to be part of the team for proposal 4 because...). You could also make an online survey, where a score is given for each RLI proposal or a poll with multiple choice question, where participants can make multiple selections to support more than one proposal.

Send out the results of the voting and the selection of RLIs with a reminder invitation if anybody would like to join a particular RLI co-design and implementation team. Send group e-mails to the teams whose proposals were selected and ask them to confirm their attendance in workshop B and invite each person to bring a +1 from their own network or choose 1 person from who has already expressed their interest and motivation to join your team. If you see that the team will be less than 12 you can also refer to their RLI proposal template and see what they wrote for 'who else is welcome' and invite people to join who you feel are suitable, trying to sustain a mix of people with lived experience, professionals and provocateurs (see section 4 for a reminder).

Time management considerations: It's recommended to have a period of 2-3 weeks between workshop A and B this gives a week for voting and 1-2 weeks for reassembling co-design teams with confirmations of attendance.

Workshop B: 'From portfolio to actionable intervention'

Workshop B happens when a Living Lab's RLI portfolio has been selected and when a co-design team for each RLI has reassembled. The workshop is best suited for 24 participants, i.e. two parallel teams of up to 12 co-designers working on their own RLIs (see figure 9). You may have smaller co-design teams and therefore have three parallel co-design tables. A minimum of 6 tables (for 4-5 people) are required to make it possible for co-design teams to breakout into three task groups during the workshop.

Figure 15 table arrangement with space to move tables for breakouts

1. Opening (15 minutes max):

Welcome and thank participants for showing up. Congratulate the co-design teams for having their RLIs selected and welcome the new members of the co-design teams. Make each team aware of each other by showing their proposals (1 slide). You can also share why you have paired the co-design teams together and that you hope they may find ways to support each other and cross-pollinate.

Then share the co-design brief for this workshop (2 slides):

Slide 1: The aim of this co-design workshop is to strengthen their RLIs and make them actionable. You have prepared some activities and templates for them to learn by doing how they prefer to cooperate and make decisions as a team. A key output you are requesting from them is a learning and action plan with an estimated budget. This is needed to activate the funding and start implementing the RLI. Assure them that the plan is not final and can be changed later on. In fact, reflexive learning sessions are a core requirement of the FoodCLIC process to make space for changing and improving the real-life interventions while they are being implemented.

Slide 2: show the parameters of the design brief, first in terms of time that it will be from now until March 2026 (22 months) organised into four cycles of action and reflection. You are requesting them to sequence the actions of the RLI into these four periods and to give more attention and detail to the first cycle that will close in September 2024 with a 'reflexive learning session' together with all the co-design teams and supporters of this FoodCLIC collaboration. Then show the three content parameters of the co-design brief: action and budget, learning and evidence, governance and care. Again, they will have templates with core questions to answer, but also open spaces to add in anything that might be missing.

2. Warm-up activity (15 minutes): 'being in the grey' spectrum line activity

Remind the participants that co-design is more about mindsets than tools. Last session we practice the mindsets of curiosity & hospitality with a warm-up activity. This time, invite them participants to practice two more mindsets for co-design: 'valuing many perspectives' and 'being in the grey'. Acknowledge that there are new members to each team who bring different perspectives to the original design and who may feel a bit in the grey. Again, hospitality and curiosity to each other is helpful. We are all probably in the grey at the moment of how to make the RLIs actionable too.

Start a spectrum line activity in the room by naming two ends of a spectrum: people who like order, planning and certainty most of the time are one end and people who like improvisation, spontaneity and uncertainty most of the time are on the end. Use figure 16 as a visual aid for the activity and invite participants to stand up and spatially place themselves along the imaginary spectrum line.

Warm-up activity:
'Being in the Grey' mindset

Place yourself along this spectrum line
Which point represents you most of the time?

Figure 16: Warm-up activity for 'being in the grey' adapted from McKercher (2020)

Ask a few people from each extreme and a few from the middle to explain they are standing there. Explain that both extremes are needed for co-design, planning allows us to move forward and agree on future actions, but too much planning and control often closes space for creativity and enjoying the process. We hope to find the right balance today.

3. Introduce consent decision-making method (10 minutes)

Before doing this activity make sure to watch the video link on figure 8 (page 15) to familiarise yourself with this decision-making method. Explain how the method works in your own words as well as explaining the benefits, e.g. very effective for making good enough decisions in small groups in relatively short times, makes space for diverse perspectives, it is quite simple to learn and also builds trust.

Explain that the remainder of session is an opportunity to experiment with consent decision-making as a way to make the learning and action plans. There will be two rounds of co-design that represent the two main parts of a consent process. The first round is **making proposal presentations** by first collecting ideas from the whole team and then breaking out into three task groups who develop three different proposals (see figure 17). The second round after the break is **re-working the proposals with the whole team to get consent** for the plans, i.e. there are no objections, it may not be perfect for everyone, but it is good enough to try out and probably change later.

If there is time you could make a humorous example. "I propose that we can all go to the toilet and take time out when we need to, are there any objections?" Pause for at least 10 seconds. Please put your thumb up if you consent to this proposal. Great as the facilitator of this proposal I announce we have all decided to go to the toilet and take time out when we need to. Congratulations everybody!"

Figure 17: Visual aid. two main parts of workshop = two main parts of consent method

4. Round 1 – collect, cross-pollinate, and develop proposals (40 minutes)

Facilitators give handouts of the original RLI proposal that was made in the last workshop. Invite them to read it and stay connected to it. There is a lot in them that can be carried into their co-designs for today. An iterative process.

Facilitators communicate the first twenty minutes will be about collecting ideas from everyone then forming into three smaller groups who develop and organise the ideas into a proposal for whole-team consent. First there's a short pair activity for the action plan with a budget, where they break down actions into three parts and place them on a timeline/cycle, then there's an individual activity of adding sticky-notes onto two templates.

Facilitator lays out a big A2 template on the table that does not have any action cards on it (see figure 18, in the top right corner) then add on the hexagon action cards that came from the original proposal (workshop A) and lay them into first and second year (top part of figure 18). Ask if any people remember proposing these actions from the last workshop and write their names on the cards. Ask the team to form pairs of 'old' and new members if possible. Give them up to 10 minutes to break down the action into three parts with three sticky-notes, e.g. action 1 is broken down into 1A, 1B, 1C. Part A is a necessary first step, Part B the core activity, Part C an extension activity that becomes possible with more support, finding etc. For each part add an estimated cost and then lay them onto the big A2 template in a time cycle (or on a timeline) that feels realistic for the activity to happen.

Figure 18: Visualisation of the end result of the pair activity

Ask everyone to put their names next to the sticky-notes that they would like to take/share responsibility and to add one more sticky-note that communicates the kind of roles they imagine playing in this intervention. This gives the breakout group a sense of what is possible as they prepare a more developed proposal.

Facilitators then ask co-design to stand up and they lay out the 2 big A2 templates (see figure 19). Ask everybody to add a maximum of four sticky-notes to each template to be fair and to not overwhelm the break out groups with too much input. Ask participants to do this individually for a maximum of 10 minutes and to respect a silent period for people to gather their own ideas. Playing some calming music can help focus.

Facilitators ask for support in moving the three tables apart, 1 table with the action plan template, 1 table with the learning and evidencing template, 1 table with the governance and care template. Invite the team to self-organise into breakout groups of at least two people per table. Inform them of the remaining time (15-20 minutes), before the break, to develop the proposals further. They may see a lot of overlap and repetition that merged or they may really like to develop some ideas further. Assure them that they do not have to integrate everything from templates. In fact, ask them to prioritise with 2-4 clear statements for each of the template boxes (see figure 19). Before closing for the break, ask the groups if they need an extra 10 minutes after the break to finish their proposal. Adjust timing accordingly.

Figure 19: Templates for individual sticky notes that breakout groups then develop into proposals

5. Break (30 minutes)

Invite the participants to rest, stay hydrated, enjoy a snack, and make use of the restrooms if they haven't already. If they are feeling nose-y, they are welcome to have a look on the tables of what's been occurring with the parallel co-design team. They are also very much welcome to fully unplug from the workshop for a while.

6. Energizer (5-10 minutes)

There are many alternative energizers online. If you have less time than planned a very quick and effective energizer is to invite everyone to stand in a circle. The aim is for everyone to clap at the same time together with their eyes closed. If you make one sound together then the energizer is complete. If there are separate clap sounds, try again (usually it works on first and second go and is funny because it's such a short and random energiser).

7. Round 2 – present and adapt for consent (45-50 minutes)

Give extra time for groups to finish their proposals. Bring the tables back together into plenary, whole team arrangement (see figure 15).

Facilitators communicate that they will be more active in the first round for team consent and hope that the following proposers will be brave to find team consent with less support from the facilitator. Start with the governance and care group proposers and remind that this is a proposal for the first cycle of action and learning (5 months) and can be changed later on as with all the other proposals.

Facilitator asks care and governance group to present their proposal in an accessible and brief way (5 minutes max) also visibly showing the template for team members to read. Invite the team members to listen carefully and to consider if they are *OK with* and therefore *give consent* for the proposal.

- Invite team members to give space to any **clarifying questions** (refraining from requesting changes) for the proposers to respond to. After clarifying, the facilitator asks team members to raise their hands if they cannot accept this proposal.

- **Re-working proposal:** If any hands are raised, ask the people with their hands raised to give a thumbs up if they can accept the proposal with some small changes or additions (typically everyone who had their hand raised switches to a thumb up). Ask the people with their thumbs up to communicate their requests for a small change or additions.
- **Consent round:** Ask if the proposers are OK to include those changes. If they are OK then go back to the whole group and ask them to show a thumb up if they consent to the proposal. If everyone has a thumb up, announce that a decision has been made and the proposal is accepted. Celebrate with a round of applause.
- **Re-work:** If everyone does not have a thumb up invite them to explain their position and to request for a change in order to tolerate the proposal. It's unlikely that this will happen, and you may find that everyone accepts the proposal without any changes or additions being requested.

Facilitators invite the learning and evidence group to propose and find team consent, with the same method as before. Ask them if they want to try and do it independently (e.g. asking for clarifying questions, objections, requests for changes and a final thumb up) or if they would like the facilitator to ask the questions as before. It can also help to remind them that consenting does not mean agreeing to do any tasks or work they do not want to do. It's really about finding approval and preventing proposals from misplaced or potentially harmful to team members who are not proposing.

If consent cannot be found on one small part of the proposal, e.g. one of the boxes in the template, you can ask the proposers if they are OK to remove this part of the proposal and to find consent for the rest of the proposal. Also it's OK to drop or pause the proposal and try again on another occasion. Repeat the consent process with the final proposing group (action plan with budget).

8. Closing activity – reflexive harvest (10-15 minutes)

Give a huge thanks to all the team members' efforts and contributions. Thank them for being brave for 'being in the grey' and for trying out the consent decision-making. Inform them that you will digitalise the learning and action plans and make a list of the actions they have planned to do before the first reflexive learning session in September with a sign-up for anyone who wants to do a particular action (point).

Ask both teams to stand on one side of the room. Ask them to reflect on any important takeaways that they can harvest from the workshop today and share with the rest of the room. Ask if anyone can start by sharing their harvest and then move to the other side of the room (this could be made more symbolic by giving everyone a bean seed which they place in a bowl in the middle of the room). Inform the group that if anyone's harvest/takeaway resonates with them a lot they can also move with the person across the room. When everyone has moved across the room, give another big

thanks to everyone and welcome them to stay around for a while and enjoy the remaining food and refreshments.

2.7 ALTERNATIVE METHODS & TOOLS

It has been a real challenge to find practical resources on how to co-design real-life interventions for food system transformation. Here are some alternative methods and practices that you find valuable enough to adapt and experiment with in your context.

Design Hackathon: This method could be a great way to generate and select RLI proposals on the scale of city-region, to refresh the process with new participants. It may even be possible to achieve the outputs (RLI proposal, portfolio selection and action and learning plan) in one event. There are concerns, however, that it would not be suitable for co-designing RLIs that centre on the neighbourhoods and therefore involving people with lived experience of food insecurity and/or very limited access to healthy sustainable food in the co-design teams. It's much more challenging to create and sustain safe spaces in large events. Therefore, it is recommended to continue building trust between stakeholder groups you have been collaborating with in previous workshops.

<https://corporate.hackathon.com/articles/design-hackathon-guide-everything-you-need-to-know>

Maximising & Evaluating Benefits of Co-design: An insightful blog on an evaluation of 144 co-design projects on tackling loneliness with a focus on how to maximise and evaluate the benefits on doing co-design. <https://www.thinknpc.org/blog/how-to-plan-effective-co-design/>

Toolkit on doing Co-design: An on-line open-source toolkit for sharing knowledge about how to do co-design led by community members and organisations. <https://co-design.inclusivedesign.ca/>

Systemic design templates: A freely accessible document that contains 30 templates for systemic design. It accompanies the book: Design Journeys through Complex Systems: Practice Tools for Systemic Design (which you must buy to access).

<https://www.systemicdesigntoolkit.org/download>

Accessible service design toolkit: Concise explanations of activities for co-design and types of representation (text, map, narrative and simulation). <https://servicedesigntools.org/tools>

2.8 NEXT STEPS & BUDGET CONSIDERATIONS

Next steps are briefly sketched in the communication of your co-design process and results as well as **budget considerations** and tips to transition co-design teams into intervention groups.

Communication

It is highly recommended that you document the co-design process in a way that it is publicly accessible. This increases trust and serves as communication material to inspire new people to join the collaboration or for other groups to experiment with intervention co-design as a progressive form of governance. In terms of accessibility, the less wordy and more visual the better.

You can include a brief description of what happened in the workshops, the outcomes of the workshops (RLI portfolio and action & learning plans), and how decisions were made. Photos and quotes from participants are also recommended. You can post the communication as a blog article on the website or social media of the FPN and/or ask for participating groups and organisations to re-post on their own social media. It's encouraged to communicate in a celebratory tone with a lot of gratitude for everyone's contributions with indication and excitement towards the next steps.

Transitioning from co-design teams to intervention groups

Co-design enables the sharing of power and ownership of the intervention. By listening to what people can do and want to do you made space for proposals to be co-generated. By including political will and commitment-making as decisive factors in selecting RLIs, it will be easier to transition into implementation. This is further supported by the making of an action and learning plan of four cycles where roles and responsibilities are defined and consented to in relation to specific actions. More support and guidance are shared in the following guidelines for 'implementing and learning from RLIs'.

For now, it's recommended to focus on the first cycle of implementation from April/May to September 2024 when the reflexive learning session will take place with space for re-planning. Focus on which actions or tasks are planned with the first cycle and activate a chosen a communication channel for each intervention group to send updates. Also, it's very likely you will be supporting collaborators to make invoices to compensate their contributions and access resources required for implementing actions.

Compensation and remuneration for co-designing

In total, each LL team has a budget of 45,000 EUR to organize at least 9 workshops in WP3 (vision; strategy; co-design x3; reflexive learning sessions x4). There is sufficient budget to compensate non-privileged members of the support team and the co-design teams. It is not recommended to compensate team members who can contribute because it is part of their job description, i.e.

professionals such as public officials, politicians, university researchers, well paid workers from big NGOs, etc.

Below is table adapted from McKersher (2020: 126-127) as a starting point, not a prescription, on thinking about payment for each group you engage with.

Table 3: Table of suggestions for compensation to support and co-design teams

Group	Compensation
Support group	Pay for their time. We can't expect people work for free or lead-codesign on top of a full day job. Community work and care work is often wrongly assumed as free. Ensure payment is offered to community partners for their time and out-of-pocket expenses. As an alternative recognition of their time, you can offer to time back to them on their own initiative.
Co-design (& implementation) teams	<p>People with lived experience (of system problems) Offer payment for time (based on complexity of activity, hours worked and emotional labour). For example, 50 euros compensation per 3-hour workshop with food and breaks. If 10 people with lived experience are part of two different RLI co-design teams (and implementation teams) attending 7 sessions (including reflexive learning) the total cost is 3,500 EUR (7.7% of total WP3 workshop budget). Inquire how your payment might impact other payments that the co-designer may receive such as welfare payments. If your institution blocks direct compensation, you can still compensate via a community partner/organisation as part of their invoice for being in the support team. They have more experience and different administrative possibilities.</p> <p>Professionals Professionals are not typically paid because the work is considered part of their day job (or an extension of it).</p> <p>Provocateurs Offer choice between these three options (plus anything else you think of)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Payment of time and out-of-pocket expenses; 2. Donation to a cause of their choice 3. A gift of time back to them in their context

FoodCLIC budget specifics

Real Life intervention budget allocated to the practice partners:

WP3 Organization workshops

Practice partners have €45.000,- for the organization of 9 workshops in WP3. The budget has also been allocated in the **category C3 'Other goods, works and services'** and could be spent on venue/catering, purchase of materials, but also on a compensation for the participants. Please

remember that cash compensation is advised against as we are not sure if the EU will compensate for this. In case don't spend all of this budget for the organization of the workshop you can also spend this money on the Real-Life Interventions within the same budget category.

WP3: Real life interventions

At the time the budget for the Real-life Interventions was allocated it was not specified as the interventions will be determined based on a co-creation process. The budget has been allocated in the **category C3 'Other goods, works and services'**. A note was included in the DoA: **Note: The costs will fulfil the general cost **eligibility** criteria indicated under Art. 6 as well as specific eligibility conditions included under Art. 6.2.C.3. The current estimates for real-life interventions are based on preliminary plans which each city-region developed. **However, further specifying these costs at this time is not meaningful given the fact that we will select interventions as part of a co-creation process.** Input for this process are the inventory of the current policy situation in each city-region and the maps of local stakeholders, food environments and food systems that will be developed in WP 2. In addition, the visions, co-developed in WP3, will play an important role. Hence, as we highly value a multi-stakeholder approach, the real-life interventions will be co- designed and implemented.*

The **C3 'Other goods, works and services'** category can include any costs needed for the implementation of the action such as consumables, material costs, translations, proofreading, legal advice, publications costs, printing costs, meeting costs like catering and venue costs, website design and development costs, etc. For 'services' it is only possible to pay an invoice for one-time service. For example, for a trainer at a workshop, a communications designer or a translator or a gardening service. It is not possible to hire someone on a structural basis, for a certain FTE for a longer period of time.

In a budget conversation between the coordination team and the EC project officer and EC financial officer the EC indicated service invoices can be accepted as long as the activities are not action tasks. *'Purchase costs (other goods and services) – Art.6.2. C.3: interventions are eligible providing the fact that they comply with best value for money/lowest prize, avoidance of conflict of interest and they are not action tasks.'* An "action task" is a task of the project described in Annex 1 (DoA). It was determined the interventions in FoodCLIC are indeed not action tasks. The interventions are co-designed, implemented and coordinated by the Living Lab teams in task 3.4: 'The implementation of the real-life interventions will take place over a period of 24 months, under the coordination of the practice partners, while research partners will be responsible for stimulating collective reflection, monitoring the process and identifying intermediate outcomes.' But the activities connected to the execution of the interventions can be considered services to the action task, and not an action task.

This means Living Lab teams have the option to reimburse the services of organizations and self-employed individuals for the work they put in the intervention. The collaborating organizations can send in an invoice for the services they have provided.

Real Life intervention budget allocated to the research partners:

The research partners of the living labs each have the following allocated for the organization for the workshops in WP3 (so part of this can also be spent on the RLI workshops):

6,000.00	WP3: workshop interaction materials
3,000.00	WP3: transcription costs
6,000.00	WP3: translation

For the reflexive learning sessions of task 3.5 the following budget has been allocated to the research partners:

12,000.00	WP3: reflexive learning sessions
14,450.00	WP3: presents participants real-life interventions

2.9 CORE REQUIREMENTS

The guidelines finalize with a **checklist** of core requirements that comprise of key considerations for co-designing real-life interventions.

As a core requirement and output of the co-design sequence, each LL team documents:

1. **A RLI portfolio of at least four interventions (inputted into D3.2 template by March 22nd)**
 - Each RLI in the portfolio is co-generated and co-decided with stakeholders and contains at least a brief description of objectives, actions/activities, who feels ownership, shared responsibilities and RMDE integration (see figure 13, page 25, for template)
 - At least 50% are designed to positively impact food environments in deprived areas_(relative to the city-region) with less access to healthy and sustainable food and where many people experience food insecurity
 - At least 50% include the generation of innovative business models to sustain and scale positive impacts beyond the two-year implementation period
2. **A provisional action & learning plan of two years for each RLI in the portfolio (by April)**
 - Describes a sequence of actions/activities in four 5–6-month cycles with clear roles and responsibilities co-decided and consented by collaborating stakeholders
 - 1st cycle is May-Sept 24', 2nd cycle is Oct-Mar 25', 3rd cycle is Mar-Sep 25', 4th and final cycle Sep-Feb 26'.
 - Documents which change(s) (i.e. objectives) an action is intended to achieve

- Including success indicators chosen and valued by participating stakeholders that can be evidenced without (over)burdening.
- Contains an estimated budget for the implementation of each RLI
- All RLIs must at least be pilotable with FoodCLIC's implementation budget meaning positive impact(s) on food environments are intended and measurable within two years with or without securing additional funding

Each RLI is required to meet these **minimum design and selection criteria** as listed in Table 2 (copied below for convenience).

Copy of Table 2: Seven core criteria for co-design and selecting RLIs

Criteria from EU-FoodCLIC DoA agreement	Criteria from city-region collaboration
1. Connects and positively impacts at least two food environments within 2 years (agri-food; community; institutional; hospitality; retail; wild)	2. Directly contributes to the collective vision of at least two food environments (generated in previous workshop)
3. Increases access to healthy sustainable food for people experiencing food insecurity AND/OR involves business model(s) for long-term production/access to healthy sustainable food	4. Directly contributes to at least one of the 4+ strategic themes, objectives or lines of action (generated in previous workshops)
5. Applies at least three of CLIC's pillars of system transformation (co-benefits; rural-urban linkages; social inclusion; connectivities with other systems and policy priorities)	6. Applies at least two additional/local criteria for selecting RLIs (co-generated with collaborators, e.g. in strategy workshop or mentimeter activity, page 13).
7. Offers possibilities for meaningful connections and cooperation with other proposed RLIs	

The core requirements of the co-design process include:

- A minimum of 3 co-design workshops, each with a minimum duration of 2 hours
- Application of a transparent decision-making method for selecting a RLI portfolio that is documented in D3.2 template and communicated to all stakeholders
- After the RLI portfolio is selected, each co-design team is limited to 12 members who co-design an action and learning plan with roles and responsibilities for implementation that all members consent to and support
- Co-design teams that centre on RLIs on food environments in deprived areas involve people with lived experience of food insecurity and/or lack of access to healthy sustainable food who are fairly compensated as co-designers. At least 1 community partner from each area is part of the support team and fairly compensated.
- Preparation, creation and facilitation of safe and caring spaces that prioritise the safety of people with lived experience (of system failures) over the comfort of professionals who tend to dominate participatory processes.

2.10 REFERENCES

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2.11 APPENDICES

Appendix A: Elaboration of Co-design & Leverage points

Defining Co-design:

“Co-design is an approach to design with, not for, people”, and involves four key principles: sharing power, prioritizing relationships, using participatory means and building capacities” (McKercher 2020). A co-designer is part of a co-design team of (mutually accountable) people with a mix of relevant lived experience, expertise and curiosity. Co-design requires a greater diversity of perspectives and partners meaning knowledge from professionals is welcomed as long as they are willing to “listen, learn and, in some cases, get out the way” (ibid). Co-design flourishes with six mindsets that new co-designers can skilfully learn from experienced coaches (see McKercher 2020).

Where participatory design asks for stakeholder feedback and tries to integrate that into *pre-generated* ideas, co-design goes a step further by working with stakeholders in partnership with equal decision-making power. This *co-generates* new relations and possibilities for different systems to emerge. Therefore, co-design reflects a movement and long-term commitment to change organisational culture and governance by practicing direct democracy. It requires increasing collective power literacy and implementing models of care for safe and non-tokenistic participation.

Figure 1: What co-design is & is not, plus the position of co-design in relation to other approaches (NEP 2023: 6-7)

An equitable approach to co-design, sensitively works across differences in power, perspective and identity to create positive change. It is an approach that encourages us to design with those “closest to the pain and furthest from power” (Pressley 2018) because those who experience oppressive pains of our food systems, such as food insecurity and precarious land access, “hold unique perspectives on how these systems need to change” (NEP 2023). There is no co-designing without co-deciding.

“At its heart, co-design is not a technical endeavour with particular steps and methods, but rather a way of being in creative relationships across power.” (NEP 2023: 5).

RLIs as leverage points:

City-region food strategies and real-life interventions are sometimes referred to as leverage points with the potential to transform complex food systems. More generally, leverage points are defined as “places in a system relatively minor interventions can lead to relatively major changes” in a system’s behaviour, interconnections, trajectory and outcomes (Fischer & Riechers 2019: 116, Meadows 1999).

They require enabling conditions –such as policy and planning actions - to scale-up and overcome resistance from incumbency, unequal power relations and other system barriers (Kok et al. 2021). Some of these enabling conditions we know before and some we learn by doing.

A recent systematic review (301 articles) of sustainability interventions found a lack of concrete examples that create transformative change (Dorninger et. al 2020). Very few interventions directly addressed or corresponded with ‘deep leverage points’ that change a system’s goals, rules, values and paradigms because they tend to be less tangible and riskier. For a schematic illustration of four realms of leverage points and their relation to deep and shallow interventions see the figure below.

copied from Fischer & Reichers (2019: 117)

Within FoodCLIC there is space to experiment, take risks and learn from attempts to radically change systemic interconnections and outcomes.

Appendix B: Transformational Convening: Principles & Actions

Whereas facilitation is about making things easier, convening is the art of inviting participants to gather and co-create great outcomes together. Convening prioritises the building mutual trust and respect which are key ingredients for engaged collaborations.

Here are four principles for convening co-design:

1. Consent-driven (invitation and inquiry instead of instructions and prescriptions, pausing and checking-in instead of rushing and pushing)
2. Visual and creative (beyond verbal and written ways of learning, connection and decision-making, e.g. drawing, sounds, theatre, visual metaphors, videos and photos, work with artists)
3. Embodied (body movement, engaging senses and emotions, space to process and play)
4. Connected to place (acknowledge local histories, include local objects, connect to natural environment outside, invite local artists, e.g. storytellers, poets and musicians to perform)

The figure below enables a comparison between transactional actions of facilitators/convenors that tend to lose trust and maintain participant engagement on the left side, and practices of transformational convening on the right side that have the opposite effect building mutual trust and respect. When we feel rushed and time scarce, it's common to fall back into transactional convening.

Which actions of transformational convening do you want to focus on in the co-design workshops and how can the support team help each to put these actions into practice?

Transactional convening	Transformational convening
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • focusing on getting through a list and pre-planned tasks • being anxious about time, taking a parental tone and telling people off for going too slow • moving on from an activity when time runs out, whether people and groups are ready or not • accepting power differences (<i>That's just the way things are</i>) • avoiding conflict that might derail the agenda and activities • operating solely in a cerebral and intellectual space • presenting and relaying information, with the illusion of effective teaching, learning or collaborating • relying on authority and a loud voice to ensure people follow tasks and pay attention • focusing on setting up physical space (e.g. presentations or chairs) while neglecting emotional safety and relationships. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • focusing on progress, being flexible and collaborative with how to get there • slowing down to support the conversations that need to be had, whether planned or unplanned • checking in with people about what they need to make quality decisions, delaying decisions where necessary • challenging power differentials and harmful behaviours • seeing conflict as necessary and generative once trust is established, sensitively and courageously exploring where tensions and disagreements exist • using the intellect, heart and gut to connect with people and sense where the energy of the team is leading • building 'connective tissue' between people to work as a team • engaging people in their discovery • sharing power, earning trust through consent (page 131) • promoting social, cultural and psychological safety.

Figure 8: Comparison: transactional & transformational convening (McKercher 2020: 129-130)

3. IMPLEMENT & LEARN FROM RLIS

These guidelines clarify core requirements, share inspiration and offer a range of options and methods for living lab coordinators and researchers to co-organize real-life interventions.

3.1 CORE REQUIREMENTS

Within FoodCLIC, a real-life intervention (RLI) is the co-design and implementation of a combination of strategic actions that work together to achieve system change. Actions will be diverse in nature, ranging from political to practical and from tangible to intangible. Within every real-life intervention a knowledge action is required to monitor and evidence impact. This enables RLIs to be tested and adapted while they are being implemented, generating supportive knowledge for accessing resources and advocating for changes in policies and planning rules.

Core requirements for implementing RLIs:

- At least four real-life interventions are implemented with multi-stakeholder work groups from now until October 2026 (24 months)
- For each action or objective of an RLI, the roles and responsibilities for realizing the action are clearly communicated and documented in an action plan, including the estimated and actual costs of all activities within an action.
- There is at least one meeting every 6 months open to all the members of an RLI work group to democratically change their action plan, i.e. adapting, adding and/or removing actions and subsequent activities.
- 50% of the work groups involve organizations that directly represent or work with/for deprived and vulnerablized communities.

Core requirements for learning from RLIs:

- Learning is organized into four cycles of action-observation-reflection-re-planning
- At least four six-monthly multi-stakeholder reflexive learning sessions are organized, including participation from each RLI work group and the policymaker CoP
- A reflexive monitoring tool, such as the Dynamic Learning Agenda, is consistently applied in each of the reflexive learning sessions enabling long-term logging and monitoring of learning
- The learning questions and knowledge requests of each RLI work group and the policymaker CoP are collected, supported, and updated within each of the four cycles

These requirements are sourced from FoodCLIC's DoA, particularly task 3.4:

“The implementation of the real-life interventions will take place over a period of 24 months, under the coordination of the practice partners, while research partners will be responsible for stimulating collective reflection, monitoring the process and identifying intermediate outcomes (T3.5).

Over this period, four six-monthly multi-stakeholder reflexive learning sessions will be organized in each LL (including food environment walks) to (1) discuss progress with respect to the activities and their intermediary outcomes, with a particular focus on translating (intermediate) outcomes into lessons/evidence to inform the policy process of T3.3; (2) identify what goes well and what needs to be improved; (3) understand barriers and make the necessary adjustments; (4) work towards required changes in local and higher-level policy and planning to remove persistent barriers to change; (5) identify innovative business models for broadening and scaling up.”

3.2 IMPLEMENTING RLIS

This section offers guidance on how to establish clear roles and responsibilities in the implementation of RLIs with action plans and memorandums of understanding (MoUs). More clarity is provided on how resources can be shared via EC-approved administration of the project budget. This is important because the number of people with remuneration and responsibilities depends on how the budget can be spent and separated in order to collaborate with different groups. Finally, there are recommendations on making space for reflection, re-design and re-planning while implementing RLIs.

3.2.1 ROLES & RESPONSIBILITIES

Establishing clear roles and responsibilities is critical to effective implementation. Roles should directly link to completing the objectives/actions that define an RLI. Responsibilities tend to be more task-specific than roles. A general role can be a community food organizer or a co-coordinator. Whereas individual responsibilities can link to specific actions or activities/tasks within an RLI such as host a skill-share, make a documentary, write funding proposals etc. There are also collective or shared responsibilities, e.g. making safer spaces and respectful communication, that can be defined in a governance and care agreement.

In the co-design stage of this FoodCLIC collaboration you were tasked with co-creating an action plan for each RLI with specific actions and activities to achieve specific objectives. An implementable action plan goes a step further by translating the actions and (sub-)activities into

tasks/responsibilities that are (self-)assigned and agreed to by people or organizations who will do them. Each activity/task of an action is also **budgeted with estimated costs**.

Akin to FoodCLIC's DoA, we recommend that for each action and activity/task in your action plan it clearly states who leads and who participates. The task leaders tend to take more responsibility, e.g. in organizing meetings, coordinating cooperation, integrating feedback and delivering a final product. [Here](#) is a link to an **RLI action plan template** that you can adapt to your situation. For more general support and templates check [here](#). It is highly recommended that for each action of a real-life intervention there is a clear understanding of the tasks that are required to implement that action.

In practice, it is usually easier for people to agree on common objectives than committing to actions that bring the objectives to fruition. In collaborative governance settings that depend on good will from many of the participants, collaboration agreements are preferred over managerial expectation setting. Collaborative leaders build trust through consensual agreements and go a step further by building commitments which attune with team members' motivations.

A **Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)** is a semi-formal method that can foster collaboration agreements and commitments within an RLI. MoUs are documents made between two or parties entering a partnership. They are often used on a certain topic (i.e. an RLI) with a certain purpose (i.e. core objectives) and related activities (i.e. actions) with tasks and responsibilities. They can increase accountability between partners; however, they are not legally binding documents nor are they formal contracts. It is recommended that you make MoUs with key/core partners in each RLI. This is particularly important for collaboration with public authorities and institutions to ensure that responsibility for implementation is shared and not unfairly dependent on the 'free will' of civil society.

[Here](#) is a useful link on how to write an MoU and here is a [basic MoU template](#) and a more [detailed MoU template](#) with (co)operational roles and responsibilities that you can adapt to your situation.

3.2.2 SHARING RESOURCES

Of equal importance to building trust and commitment from a RLI work group is their resourcing via compensation for their services and reimbursement of material costs, such as healthy sustainable food. In total, each LL team has a budget of at least 95.000 EUR to implement RLIs (T3.4) and 45.000 EUR to organize at least nine multi-stakeholder workshops, of which four are reflexive learning sessions.

The project manager of FoodCLIC has met with each of the living lab teams to collect your preliminary requests and enquiries on how the implementation budget can be spent.

For example:

- *If we cannot hire a co-coordinator for each intervention, what is possible?*
- *Can we rent kitchen space and farmland for an extended period?*
- *What alternatives exist if those implementing cannot send invoices, e.g. options for volunteer reimbursements?*
- *Are there limits to how many invoices a collaborating partner can make?*

The sharing of less tangible resources, such as knowledge products, public recognition, networking or advocacy may even be more valuable to stakeholders than financial resources. You can find more ideas or guidance on sharing these resources in sections 3.3.3 and 4 of this document.

3.2.3 ADAPTING RLIS: REFLECT, REDESIGN, REPLAN

Adaptive governance promotes the evolution of RLIs in response to changes in understanding, objectives and context, such as the emergence of new barriers. Within each action are micro theories of change, i.e. we do this for that effect, which we can effectively test when we are clear on the success indicators or intended impacts of each action. We cannot, however, adapt RLIs without first receiving and reflecting on feedback. How can we make informed decisions based on what we measured and what everyone experienced as the effects of RLI actions with broader systemic interactions?

An action plan for each RLI is a vital tool to document, communicate and track which actions are planned into the implementation of each RLI. It serves as an important organizing and memory device that you can return to cyclically and record any adaptive changes in the design of a RLI, i.e. new actions or different (sub-)activities. Such changes are likely as we *learn from RLIs* via informed reflections and make shared spaces for re-designing and re-planning.

3.3 LEARNING FROM RLIS

This section offers guidelines on how to organize reflexive monitoring within four semi-structured action-learning cycles. A vital bridge between the cycles are the four reflexive learning sessions. A guideline is provided on how to organize these sessions with the application of the Dynamic Learning Agenda (DLA). Finally, there are strategic considerations and recommendations in collecting and communicating feedback, lessons learned and results of the RLIs. Feedback storylines, storyboards and most significant change (MSC) are recommended as complementary transdisciplinary methods.

3.3.1 REFLEXIVE MONITORING IN CYCLES

Reflexive monitoring is a dynamic and iterative process that fosters continuous learning and improvement within a food system project. By systematically reflecting on experiences, engaging with stakeholders, and adapting to changing circumstances, project teams can enhance their effectiveness and contribution to positive outcomes within a food system and beyond.

Figure 20: FoodCLIC's projected transdisciplinary action-research spiral

Figure 20 visualises how FoodCLIC organises reflexive monitoring into four cycles of action-observation-reflection-re-planning. The reflexive learning sessions (see section 3.3.2) are a key moment that represents the end and beginning of a cycle of transdisciplinary action research or learning. By doing actions with a plurality of stakeholders and reflecting on them together, we are

more likely to learn holistically and co-create integrated solutions. Cycles can become a progressive spiral when the learning leads to adaptations in RLI action plans and builds commitment, capacities and resources for their implementation.

The following guideline facilitates the reflexive monitoring process and will provide structured frameworks for documenting our goals/objectives, obstacles/barriers, successes/strengths, learning questions, and continuing plans, enabling us to systematically track progress and make informed decisions moving forward.

5 key ingredients of reflexive monitoring

1. **Self-Reflection:** Reflexive monitoring starts with the project team reflecting on their own actions, decisions, and processes. This involves asking questions like: Are we effectively implementing our planned activities? Are there any unexpected challenges or opportunities that have arisen? Are we staying true to our project objectives?
2. **Learning and Adaptation:** Based on the insights gained through self-reflection, the project team can then identify areas for improvement or adjustment. This might involve refining project strategies, reallocating resources, or changing course in response to new information or changing circumstances. The goal is to enhance the project's effectiveness and maximize its impact.
3. **Multi-stakeholder Engagement:** Reflexive monitoring also involves engaging with stakeholders to gather diverse perspectives on the project's progress and outcomes. This might include beneficiaries, partners, funders, and other relevant actors. By soliciting feedback and input from stakeholders, the project team can gain valuable insights and ensure that their efforts are aligned with the needs and priorities of those they seek to serve.
4. **Contextual Analysis:** In addition to evaluating the project itself, reflexive monitoring involves analyzing the broader socio-economic, political, (inter)cultural and environmental context as well as the history and dynamics of the FPN in which the project operates. This helps to identify external factors that may influence the project's success or failure, and to adapt strategies accordingly.
5. **Documentation and Reporting:** Reflexive monitoring requires thorough documentation of the project's activities, outputs, and outcomes, as well as the learning process itself. This documentation serves as a basis for ongoing reflection, as well as for reporting to stakeholders and sharing lessons learned with the wider community.

3.3.2 REFLEXIVE LEARNING SESSIONS

In this section a guideline in the form of a facilitator script is offered on how to organize the four rounds of reflexive learning sessions by using a Dynamic Learning Agenda (DLA). Note: this is one way of doing a reflexive learning session – of course this has to be adapted to your local context!

The DLA is a method to facilitate reflection and learning in action to overcome complex and difficult change processes through the analysis of barriers and opportunities and the formulation of learning questions for food system transformation. Here is a link to the downloadable DLA tool. <https://knowledgehub.fit4food2030.eu/resource/dynamic-learning-agenda-dla/>

When, where and with whom?

The first round of reflexive learning sessions takes place +/- September 2024, followed by another 3 rounds of reflection sessions every 5-6 months. At the level of the RLIs, these sessions can be planned and embedded in the overall agreements or MoUs you make with regard to collaboration and communication with the RLI partners.

Each round of reflexive sessions consists of one session per RLI, inviting all participating partners of the RLI. When cross-fertilization between RLIs is desirable, these can take place at the same time, in the same location, but with a facilitator for each RLI present. These sessions at the RLI-level are followed up by a session at the level of the city-region with actors at this level (“policy-makers” (if you have any direct connection to formal policy-makers), people in bodies of government or people representing (non-)profit private initiatives, those involved in the FPNs, etc.). If you work with different municipalities, it would be great to bring these together in one session but that may not always be desirable depending on the local politics and context of course. The outcome of the sessions at the level of the RLI will feed into these city-region-scale sessions to allow for policy-learning.

Tentative outline of a reflection session programme

Time: 2-4 hours – the timing indicated here (indicative, not set in stone of course!) are for a 2-hour session.

Step 1: Getting started – 10 minutes

To get into the session, an introduction outlining the purpose of the session, the programme of the session and re-stating what the RLI is about, i.e. its objectives and actions, would be helpful.

The purpose of each reflexive session is to take a step back, and reflect: what have we learned so far, how much progress we have made, what do we need to learn next to realize the ambitions of this RLI, and what does this imply for our actions for the next 5 months?

Step 2: How much progress have we made? – 20 minutes

This step would be a presentation by the LL team of both the baseline and measurements thereafter of the core and home-grown set of indicators (10 minutes) followed by discussion with the RLI partners on what these numbers/indicators mean – overall, how successful do they feel they have been? (10 minutes). You can ask people to write down, e.g. on post-it notes, what they considered particularly successful, i.e. strengths, over the past period, for example.

The point of this step is to lay the foundations to start discussing obstacles/barriers that they have faced. Most likely, the discussion will naturally flow from ‘how successful have we been so far, what have we achieved already’ to ‘what obstacles are we facing’ (i.e. why some activities have not yet been realized). If that happens, you will naturally transition to the next step.

Step 3: Discussing obstacles and formulating learning questions – 30 minutes

During this step, you moderate a discussion on the obstacles that RLI partners have been facing. It can be helpful to work with smaller break-out groups if the total group is large or if there are sensitive topics or groups who are not always easily heard when consensus becomes the focus right away. This is crucial, given the re-planning in step 5, where it is really important that not only dominant groups’ interests are represented in the learning questions but also those of groups who are less resourced and/or less heard etc. So please design your session in appropriate break-out groups (or possibly different events where different ‘kinds’ of partners come together across the RLIs!) and with perhaps several moderators. Overall: there is of course a lot of space, flexibility and different ways in which this can be organized – how to strike the best balance of feasibility and providing room for everyone to take part equally well is different for each LL...

As a moderator, you want to get the discussion to become as precise/detailed as possible – e.g. rather than discussing, for example “that capitalism is the problem”, try to bring out what precisely happened in particular instances, and also ask people which ambition is hindered because of the obstacle they faced.

The purpose of this discussion is to come to a deeper understanding of the obstacles/barriers that are being faced and to formulate so-called learning questions. These learning questions look like this:

How **can** I/we (ambition), **while** (obstacle)?

On the first set of dots, you fill in an ambition, on the second set of dots you can fill in an obstacle that is either experienced or anticipated. So, for example, a learning question could be: “How can we access currently unused land in the neighborhood, while we do not know who manages access to public land in the municipal offices?”

You want the formulation of these learning questions to be as precise as possible – and by moderating the discussion in such a way that you gain a more and more precise understanding of the obstacle that is being faced, you implicitly already discuss what has been learned about the obstacle so far, and really get to the “edge” of things.

The above will be different for the second, third and fourth reflection session. In that case, you will re-evaluate the learning questions during this session: which questions have been resolved, and which ones need to be edited, based on progressive learning? Which new obstacles were faced, requiring new learning questions to be developed?

How to formulate these learning questions? You can, of course, ask people during the reflection session to formulate these questions themselves, or give people at least the opportunity to do so. However, if people don't come up with learning questions themselves, which is likely without significant scaffolding, you may distill these questions from the discussion on obstacles and progress. In either case it is helpful to bring flip-overs to write these questions down and to crosscheck them with the RLI partners present in the session: do they capture the discussion adequately?

Step 4: break – 15 minutes

Step 5: looking ahead & re-planning – 45 minutes

Based on the foregoing, it is crucial to re-evaluate RLI actions and (sub-)activities, including the assignment of roles and responsibilities, that were planned originally: what can be done to respond to the learning questions – i.e. make the “how can I/we” part of the question possible, and who can take responsibility?

For example, continuing with the same learning question as above – if you formulated the following question (“How can we access currently unused land in the neighborhood, while we do not know who manages access to public land in the municipal offices?”), you may want to plan an activity to enquire at the municipal office who manages access to public land.

Ideally, at the end of the session, you end up with a list of (re)formulated learning questions and a revised action plan. In case you do run out of time, living lab researchers can log the learning questions with a template (see Section 4) and living lab coordinators can integrate action/activity proposals from the session into a revised action plan to send to partners for final editions and approval.

Summary of the steps for a reflexive learning session

- **Step 1:** In the first step of our reflexive monitoring process, we identify our RLI's destination and find out where we want to go.
- **Step 2:** As we progress towards, we encounter various obstacles and challenges. These could include resource constraints, logistical hurdles, stakeholder resistance, or unexpected external factors. It's important to systematically identify and assess these obstacles to understand their impact on our trajectory.
- **Step 3:** Despite the obstacles we face, we also achieve success in reaching our local indicators. These are the specific milestones or indicators of progress that we've set for ourselves within the FoodCLIC collaboration. We use monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to measure our progress against these indicators and assess how far we've come towards our ultimate goals.
- **Learning Questions:** Through this process, learning questions will be generated that help us deepen our understanding of our dynamics and outcomes of the interventions. These questions may include: What factors contributed to our success in achieving certain indicators? What lessons can we learn from the obstacles we encountered? How can we leverage our successes to overcome future challenges?
- **Continuing Plan:** To ensure that FoodCLIC continues to progress and evolve, it needs to develop a continuing action plan based on reflections and learning from the monitoring process. This plan outlines the actions and (sub-)activities we will take to address identified obstacles, build on successes, and adapt strategies as needed to stay on course towards the respected objectives of each RLI.

Facilitator & Moderator Q&A:

1. How to ensure everyone has the space to make their own learning questions while maximising time for group reflections on most important questions?

You can scaffold the learning question making by writing sentence starters on post-it notes. Every participant receives a post-it notes and voices their learning question (LQ). Each participant is then given two dot stickers to vote for LQs they want to discuss, which are not their own. A short time can be allowed to merge questions with consent from the question makers before voting. Dedicate at least 30 minutes to discuss and reflect around 2 of the most voted, i.e. prioritise, LQs. See figure 21 for a visualisation of this practice.

Figure 21: Prioritizing self-generated learning questions for group discussions

2. What if a minority stakeholder, such as a community organisation, does not get their learning question addressed because it (always) receives too few dot votes?

All the learning questions that were generated in a reflexive learning session should be recorded in a DLA reporting template with the name of the question maker. In the next reflexive learning sessions these LQs are listed and made visible to all the participants. If the question maker decides to ask the same question from before they gain, for example, 5 dot votes, to significantly increase their chance of being high on the agenda. If the question is no longer pertinent, they can generate new learning questions.

Additionally, you can theme a reflexive learning session which allows for one learning question to be addressed from a particular stakeholder group. For example, the first session could give some focus to municipal stakeholders and the second session on civil society or community-based organisations.

3. What if there is a large group for a reflexive learning session e.g. 20+ participants?

If you have many partners involved in RLI work group, e.g. 12+ participants, it makes sense to have two group discussions simultaneously. You can use the same practice or method to generate LQs and prioritise them (figure 2) with a moderator for each table. We recommend that a moderator can receive some kind of briefing and practice on the structure/formula of a learning question for a DLA. Furthermore, they can use a template for logging the group reflections and proposed activities around a learning question (see section 3.5: Appendix DLA). This makes it far easier to log the learning question, reflections and lessons learned across the course of the FoodCLIC collaboration.

4. How do I make the reflexive learning sessions concretely support the implementation of RLIs?

Instead of making an open space for new ambitions, you can ask the participants to select ambitions from the action plan when formulating their learning questions. The ambitions can be objectives of the RLI or a planned action to achieve a particular RLI objective. This requires a printing of an action plan with as few words as possible so participants can draw from it in the session. This guides reflections directly on what we planned to do, what barriers we encountered or anticipate(d) and what can we do to make progress. Again, it is important to distribute sufficient time for re-planning in the reflexive learning sessions with a focus on concrete changes in actions or (sub-)activities that are feasible within an action-learning cycle. This should enable the formation of learning questions that are answered by experimentally improving the implementation process.

3.3.3 SHARING LEARNINGS & RESULTS

Throughout the implementation of the FoodCLIC collaboration it is important to make space to receive, share and respond to feedback, not only during reflexive learning sessions. There are several creative methods that can complement the sessions with impactful storytelling. Furthermore, equitable participation can be fostered whereby historically marginalised communities articulate feedback and make effective affective requests or proposals.

Feedback Storylines can take a variety of forms (and formats). In the end, the most important thing is to convey the key aspects of the RLI as chosen by the community, and in a manner that those creating the storylines can commit to. For example, <https://unalab.enoll.org/storylines/>

The **Storyboard** is a graphical technique that helps you understand stakeholders across a specific process of implementation. It includes pictures or drawings that focus on the experience of stakeholders in the RLI. For example, <https://unalab.enoll.org/storyboard/>

Both methods could be offered to and co-created with a particular stakeholder group who may be experiencing a particular issue or challenge within the FoodCLIC collaboration. With consent, the products of these methods could be shared in the following reflexive learning session for positive outcomes, such as building empathy and finding relational solutions. They can also be used to creatively communicate lessons learned via stories of experimentation.

Most Significant Change (MSC)

The MSC technique is another qualitative form of participatory monitoring and evaluation that can be done in between or in preparation for reflexive learning sessions. It is particularly valuable for collecting and analysing data on changes attributable or connectable to the actions of RLI, i.e. results as well as capturing unexpected learnings.

“Essentially, the process involves the collection of significant change (SC) stories emanating from the field level, and the systematic selection of the most significant of these stories by panels of designated stakeholders or staff. The designated staff and stakeholders are initially involved by ‘searching’ for project impact. Once changes have been captured, various people sit down together, read the stories aloud and have regular and often in-depth discussions about the value of these reported changes. When the technique is implemented successfully, whole teams of people begin to focus their attention on program impact.”

(Davies & Dart 2005: 8)

Chapter 1 of the MSC guide gives a 10-minute overview, chapter 2 gives 10 steps to implementing and chapter 3 is about trouble shooting. The full guide and the aforementioned chapters can be accessed [here](#). As with storylines and storyboards, MSC takes a story approach to monitoring and learning from RLIs without using pre-defined indicators that have to be measured or counted. For more information and guidance, especially in relation to indicators please refer to FoodCLIC’s RMDE framework.

3.4 COMMUNICATING & ARCHIVING

Translating the intermediate outcomes or results of the real-life interventions into lessons, good practices and evidence for structural changes, i.e. policy and planning change (T3.3), requires skillful and plural means of communication. This section offers recommendations for communicating and archiving the implementation and learning from RLIs to support co-benefits across scales and multi-stakeholder groups. It serves as a starting point because we trust that you will co-create more responsive and context-appropriate ways that align with your capacities and the preferred forms of knowledge from your stakeholders.

Before & After Reflexive Learning Sessions
 Before a reflexive learning session, it is recommended that the LL team, led by LL researcher(s), prepares a short presentation (10 minutes) of both the baseline and measurements thereafter of the core and home-grown set of indicators (see step 2 of Section 3B). This can promote and guide discussions and reflections with the RLI partners, e.g. the meaning(s) of the measurements and the ongoing success/progress of the RLI. You may want to consider experimenting with infographics to

better communicate dense data and combining with story-based approaches like those included in Section 3C.

After a reflexive learning session, it is recommended that the LL team make a short transversal report for each of the RLI groups and the policymaker CoP. They can be sent as an e-mail newsletter and/or uploaded onto a FPN website to make a digital archive that is open-access. The recommended key components of the report are some visual products, key reflections on progress (with some links to success indicators/measurements), the learning questions that were prioritized and discussed, and any editions/additions that were made to the action plan for the next cycle of action learning and implementation.

RLI Action Plans & Reflexive Learning Reports

For the living lab coordinators, the RLI action plan is the key document that enables the recording and tracking of actions and (sub-)activities. An [adaptable RLI action plan template](#) (excel file) has been made which has a tab for each RLI. To record any changes or adaptations that are made from moments of reflection and replanning use a different colour, e.g. changes after cycle one in green, after cycle two in orange, and so on. It is important that changes are transparent and consented to by RLI partners because they also lead to changes in roles, responsibilities and/or budget spending. This is also important information for the overall reporting and costing of the project for funders.

For the living lab researchers, a reflexive learning report is the key documents that enables the recording and tracking of learning and qualitative impact across the four cycles of action learning. It is recommended to work with the DLA approach as explained in practical terms with guidelines on facilitating reflexive learning sessions. An [adaptable DLA reporting template](#) (excel file) has been made which has a tab for each RLI and the policymaking CoP. The template and the guidelines were developed and adapted from long-term experience of research and practice partners in a similar EU-horizon project of food system transformation called [Fusili](#).

It is highly recommended to be consistent with your approach to organizing reflexive learning sessions and reporting on the learning across all four cycles. This will support all the partners to become more competent in the approach and support the systematization of learning and impact by coherently tracking change over time. Furthermore, if all living lab teams make space for key findings/results and lessons learned, as is accommodated in the guidelines and DLA reporting template, we enable comparative analysis and learning across living lab teams and extension city-regions (task 4.4 and deliverable 3.3)

Responding to Plural Knowledge Needs

What else is there to communicate beyond adaptations to RLI action plans and transversal reports/summaries of RLI learnings and results consolidated in reflexive learning sessions? The answer very much depends on the knowledge needs, in content as much as form, of the RLI partners and policymakers. For example, university partners may need more scientific knowledge

to sufficiently prove an impact than community partners who may need short-form and social media-friendly knowledge. Policy makers may need more formal communication, such as policy briefs.

We cannot give guidelines on this, except to keep responding to requests from partners and/or keep asking partners what kinds of knowledge and communications they need to answer their learning questions. What kinds of knowledge and communications do they/we need or prefer to contribute to food system change by evidencing their impact, accessing more support or advocating for changes in policy and planning processes? Figure 22 shows the results of an activity we did in the kick-off of these guidelines. It shows the range of knowledge forms and spaces for sharing knowledge between community/civil society, local government/public admin and university partners.

Figure 22: Multi-stakeholder knowledge forms and spaces

FoodCLIC Forum: Discourse.org

Last but not least, is our [FoodCLIC Forum](#) on discourse.org. This is a mutual-support space that allows you to share anything that may support you/us in the FoodCLIC collaboration and beyond. Such sharing allows for specific and decentralized support and also feeds into the preparation of whole group monthly support meetings. This is normal text in 'Roboto' font.

3.5 APPENDIX

APPENDIX DLA – Log sheet for reflexive learning session

Please, use one sheet per learning question.

State a key ambition or objective (from an action plan) that you find difficult to achieve:	
When was this ambition/objective first articulated?	
<i>Notice that one aim may generate several learning questions, each corresponding to <u>one</u> significant barrier. Thus, the aim just stated may serve as the starting point for setting up several log sheets, each corresponding to a separate barrier</i>	
Mention one significant barrier making it difficult to achieve the above ambition:	
State your learning question in the following form (ambition + barrier):	
How can I/we achieve...	
...while...	?
How can the barrier be overcome? Which resources/opportunities exist in this system/network?	
How can I/we* contribute to a positive outcome? Activities or tasks for revised action plan:	
*Please only propose what you are willing to implement	

If these activities or tasks are implemented, what effects are projected?
Date when aim was realized:
<i>Please use the backside of the log sheet to make notes on what you are doing in following up the learning question and its associated action plan, and what you learn on the way. What worked, what didn't work, why, etc.? Also, if relevant, report any revisions of the learning question or of the systems analysis that is taking place.</i>

Adapted from [Fit4Food: Dynamic Learning Agenda Tool](#)

4. SET-UP & RUN A POLICYMAKER COP

These guidelines clarify core requirements, share inspiration and offer a range of options and methods for living lab coordinators and researchers to set up and run a Community of Practice (CoP) for policymakers within the Food Policy Networks (FPNs) of their respected city-region contexts. CoPs for policymakers can be a vital space to strengthen and scale RLIs during the implementation phase and sharing of great practices. Integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks are prioritized as the domain of shared interest for the prospective CoP as well as attention to the practices, knowledge exchange and capacity building which may support such systemic changes.

4.1 WHY ESTABLISH A COP FOR POLICYMAKERS?

A CoP for policymakers has the potential to generate benefits for all the partners involved in the FoodCLIC collaboration.

Policymakers can benefit by:

1. Gaining strategic context-sensitive and evidence-based understandings of how systemic interventions can change food environments and meet policy goals
2. Build capacities for multi-stakeholder governance by experimenting with practices of collaborative, reflexive and adaptive governance
3. Being supported by a diverse and active FPN to strengthen and champion recommendations and proposals for changes in policy and planning

Real-life intervention (RLIs) work groups can benefit by:

1. Sharing relevant learning questions and knowledge needs to the CoP for policymakers who may be able to provide relevant institutional, political and technical knowledge
2. Informing, proposing and/or receiving concrete policy actions supportive of their RLIs and efforts for healthy, just and sustainable food environments and systems

Living lab coordinators and researchers can benefit by:

1. Building trust and inter-sectoral relationships with policy makers
2. Enhancing their skills in moderation and facilitation of institutional boundary-bridging to foster innovative food system transformations
3. Strengthening exchange and translation of (city-region) food strategies into concrete proposals and recommendations for policy and planning actions

Within FoodCLIC's Description of Action (DoA), the formation of a policy and planning CoP within a FPN is a clear way to establish and strengthen a FPN and a Living Lab team (T3.1). It is understood as providing the "foundations to translate city-region food strategies into integrated food policies" and food-sensitive planning frameworks (T3.2) by being a supportive space for policymakers to "build competences for context-sensitive policies and planning through repeated engagement with societal actors in Tasks 3.2, 3.3 & 3.4". Finally, within Task 3.4 the CoP is conceived as the suitable space for communicating and "translating (intermediate) outcomes [of RLI activities] into lessons/evidence to inform the policy process of T3.3" and a space to "work towards local and higher-level policy and planning to remove persistent barriers to change".

4.2 KEY COMPONENTS

This section shares a working definition of a CoP for policymakers by engaging with three key components: (1) the policymakers, (2) the practice(s), and (3) the community.

Generally, "communities of practice are groups of people who share a concern or passion for something they do (a domain) and learn how do it better as they interact regularly" ([Wenger-Trayner 2015](#)). There is "no one-recipe-fits-all" to CoPs and there are several myths to be wary of which the originators debunk (see Appendix). Size, membership and ways of working are dynamic and can change over time.

Aligning to FoodCLIC's DoA, a CoP for policymakers is a group of people who share a concern or passion for healthy, just and sustainable food environments and food systems and hold to make integrated food-policies and food-sensitive planning which they learn how to do better as they interact regularly.

Who are the policymakers?

In a formal and power-concentrated sense, policymakers are people in bodies of government in each of the cities and towns of the city-region, including those of relevant private parties and institutions (school boards, hospitals, etc.). They tend to hold positions of strong institutional power to decide and execute policy and planning (actions), such as food procurement, the contents and budget allocations of a food strategy, or the strategic goals or land use agreements for urban/spatial development.

Who counts as a policymaker is likely to vary depending on many factors, such as the networks, interpersonal skills, and political capital of yourselves and the collaborating FPNs. The practice partners of some LL teams are positioned within specific municipalities and department (civil servants) facilitating connections to particular policy makers while also creating challenges to connect beyond jurisdictions. Some LL practice partners are positioned within progressive civil

society-led FPNs which may make direct connections to policymakers even more challenging. Such situations may require a strategic broadening and informalizing of who counts as a policymaker within the CoP and what can be the core functions and practices of the CoP (see section 4A for strategic considerations).

What is being practiced?

Generally, CoPs strengthen and grow their practices through a variety of meaningful activities. Figure 23 shows some typical examples. Directly relating to food system transformation, there is the [‘National Right to Food’ CoP](#) in the U.S. which centres on shared learning and the provision **technical support** and **capacity building** for the development of informed and coordinated food and farm policy and advocacy’. The [‘Food Systems Approach on the Ground’ CoP](#), facilitated by UNEP, adds the activities of a **webinar series** and **‘joint engagement at global events to advocate a food systems approach’** to support practices of upscaling best practices and strengthening food system governance.

What do communities of practice look like?

Communities develop their practice through a variety of activities. The following table provides a few typical examples:

Problem solving	“Can we work on this design and brainstorm some ideas; I’m stuck.”
Request for information	“Where can I find the code to connect to the server?”
Seeking experience	“Has anyone dealt with a customer in this situation?”
Reusing assets	“I have a proposal for a local area network I wrote for a client last year. I can send it to you and you can easily tweak it for this new client.”
Coordination and synergy	“Can we combine our purchases of solvent to achieve bulk discounts?”
Building an argument	“How do people in other countries do this? Armed with this information it will be easier to convince my Ministry to make some changes.”
Growing confidence	“Before I do it, I’ll run it through my community first to see what they think.”
Discussing new developments	“What do you think of the new CAD system? Does it really help?”
Documenting projects	“We have faced this problem five times now. Let us write it down once and for all.”
Visits	“Can we come and see your after-school program? We need to establish one in our city.”
Identifying gaps in competence	“Who knows what, and what are we missing? What other groups should we connect with?”

Figure 23: General CoP activities (Wenger-Trayner 2015)

There is also [Feast's CoP for Food & Health](#) with 19 European LLs that co-organizes monthly **knowledge brokerage sessions** based on deep-dive thematic cases proposed by the CoP members themselves. Finally, there is a [Regional Food Policy Council CoP](#) that **develops resources and materials** to support regional approaches and the [WHO's Food Systems CoP](#) that provides **monthly updates and peer-to-peer learning activities** to “streamline and expand quality technical information over time”. All of these CoPs provide arenas for coordination and collaboration on joint activities and they all strengthen policy-practice-science interfaces by involving policymakers, practitioners and researchers as members.

Why a community?

A key advantage of a CoP approach is the foregrounding of interpersonal relationships that were reported as the primary enablers of successful engagements between municipal officers and university researchers in 188 collaborative civic policy projects (Carroll & Crawford 2024). The building of mutually-supportive, respectful and caring relationships makes safe-enough-spaces to cross organisational and professional boundaries, combine perspectives and new possibilities. By attending to relations it becomes possible to build sufficient trust and empathy of each other's context to transform challenges and knowledge exchanges into action points. A community takes time to understand each other's ways of working and institutional barriers.

4.3 CORE REQUIREMENTS

The core requirements of a CoP for policymakers are:

1. LL teams facilitate opportunities for policymakers to build capacities in multi-stakeholder/participatory governance (collaborative, reflexive and adaptive governance) and integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning
2. LL teams set up or strengthen a pre-existing CoP with at least three policymakers and planners who participate in at least four reflexive learning sessions (which at least once coincide with the reflexive learning sessions of the relevant RLI work groups)
3. LL teams facilitate that CoP members to learn from each other and from the reflexive learning sessions of the relevant RLI work groups
4. LL teams translate (intermediate) outcomes and challenges from the RLI action-research cycles and RMDE activities into lessons, evidence and other valuable forms of knowledge that are beneficial to the CoP for policymakers
5. LL teams routinely check-in on members' interests, needs and capacities for learning and collaboration to make the CoP as valuable as possible (e.g. based on the needs LL teams may invite certain stakeholders to present at a CoP session)

6. The CoP for policymakers formulate, recommend and/or respond to evidence-based and concrete policy and planning actions to support healthy, just and sustainable food environments and food systems
7. The CoP for policymakers are given space to propose a mixture of activities for shared learning and capacity building with at least two activities open to the public and taking place in public spaces
8. The CoP for policymakers is part of a FPN and the minutes or outcomes of each meeting or activity are communicated to members of the FPN in an appropriate form

4.4 SETTING UP A COP

Setting up a policymaker CoP requires strategic considerations. The composition and functions of the CoPs are highly context-dependent, therefore the guidelines are as flexible and open as possible. The LL governance event can serve to establish or revitalize the CoP while the RLI reflexive learning sessions can provide an anchor.

Strategic considerations

Below are some strategic considerations to set up a policymaker CoP:

Scale: Consider which scale is most appropriate and has most potential and momentum for changes in policy and planning. For example, the LL team of Amsterdam city-region currently co-organises a city-regional CoP together with the MRA Bureau – based in the FPN of Voedsel Verbindt – where the focus is on supporting smaller municipalities interested in making a food strategy. The MRA Bureau has made budget available for the CoP for coordination and activities.

Flexibility: If you work with different municipalities or departments, it is ideal to bring them together into one CoP session but that may not always be desirable on the local politics and context of course. Flexibility is required to communicate relevant outcomes of the RLI action-learning cycle to policymakers and feed them into broader, city-regional or inter-sectorial CoP sessions for integrated policy learning.

Adaptability: Each LL team is considerably dependent on pre-existing relations of the FPN they have joined and/or are building, they tend to be the primary enabler of research-policy interaction (Carroll & Crawford 2024). If there are not yet direct links with policymakers, the CoP can be adapted to a 'policy-making CoP' where a diversity of FPN members can formulate, recommend and propose policy and planning actions to external policymakers. Alternatively, if progressive food policies

already exist it might make more sense to focus on using the CoP to support the responsible policymakers and planners with its effective implementation.

Sensitivity: Consider which policymakers are most relevant for the RLIs the LL is implementing and vice versa. Which opportunities and barriers exist for the flourishing or upscaling on the RLIs and who has the power to change things? It is unlikely these people are ‘policy entrepreneurs’ who value co-creation, are open to experience, unconventional and can influence and mobilise others (Timmerman et al. 2014). Many municipal policymakers are time-scarce, risk-averse and afraid to share power. Many are more used to the traditional roles of provider and mediator than the progressive roles of co-creator and innovator (see figure 24 below). Therefore, sensitivity is required in what can be asked for, and also patience in the making of experiences that gradually build capacities and confidence towards innovation and co-creation roles in a safe-enough and supporting space such as a CoP.

	Provider	Mediator	Co-creator	Innovator
Activities	Inform members, authorize or end subsidies and permits, check if rules are followed.	Collect information, listen and support members, bring parties together, deal with tension.	Collaborate with members as equal partners, deal with tension.	Experiment (social prototyping, interventions) together with members, deal with tension.

Figure 24: Four roles of municipal policymakers (Vos 2017: 14)

More considerations or design principles for creating effective and self-sustaining CoPs can be found in figure 25 below.

Principle	Example
Design for evolution	Ensure scope for evolution to meet interests of participants within the area of interest
Open dialogues	Encourage discussion to enable sharing of perspectives from outside the COP
Encourage different levels of participation	Ensure a combination of core members (full and regular contribution), regular (active contribution) and peripheral (often largely observers with occasional contribution)
Develop both public and private community spaces	The core COP may have its regular "private" spaces for interaction, but also contribute to public spaces, e.g. through blogs, sessions at conferences
Focus on value	Identify what the COP most values, and then focus discussion and activities around these
Combine familiarity and excitement	Introduce radical or challenging discussion ideas as well as the more common concerns
Create a rhythm for community	Regular schedule of activities and/or focal points that regularly bring participants together

Figure 25: principles for creating effective and self-sustaining CoPs (Vincent et al. 2018: 75)

Linking to governance event & reflexive learning sessions

The FPN's convening of a LL governance event (T3.3) is an important opportunity to communicate the designs of the RLIs and celebrate the beginning of their implementation. It is viable means to attract policymakers and planners to become part of a CoP and participate in the governance of the FoodCLIC project.

During the first half of the event, it is advised to focus on understanding how the collaborative, reflexive and adaptive governance of the RLIs is suited to provide contextualised-evidence and inform integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks. The second half of the event, which can be on the same day or not, would focus on the establishment of the CoP with an experience of reflexive governance. Members reflect on relevant learning questions and outcomes from the RLI reflexive learning sessions and decide on their own learning questions. Space is made for them to propose or feedback on the potential design of the CoP. For more guidance on the LL governance event, please refer to section 5.

The RLI reflexive learning sessions act as the bridge between the action-learning cycles of the RLIs where the RLI working groups reflect on their collaboration to effectively re-plan or adapt their intervention. They can be a great source of learning and insight for policymakers and planners to understand systemic interactions across food environments. It is required that the CoP meets at least four times in the 24-month cycle to do their own tailor-made reflexive learning sessions in relation to the four cycles of action-learning. It is recommended that the policymakers and planners can join a RLI work group and also participate in their sessions too. For more guidance on how to facilitate the reflexive learning sessions with a Dynamic Learning Agenda, please refer to section 3.3.2.

4.5 RUNNING A COP

According to Vincent et al. (2018: 74) a CoP “has the potential to survive past the initial burst of post-workshop enthusiasm... if common aims emerge, and the community recognises the potential gains of active participation, under the leadership of key individuals”.

Towards self-organization

While running the CoP, it is important to cultivate the conditions for it to become increasingly self-organised and run a life of its own. The FoodCLIC project should serve as a catalyst to the formation of enduring CoPs which outlive the project. This is why it is vital to embed the CoP within an FPN. The LL team offers to facilitate reflexive learning sessions and translate lessons and evidence from the RLI and RMDE activities while the FPN should play an active role in recruiting new members and deciding the form and function of the CoP.

CoPs tend to excel when engagement is “nurtured, rather than controlled and managed” (Carroll & Crawford 2024: 14). High quality moderation is also a vital factor in the quality of CoPs and it is recommended that the CoP members can nominate moderators with payment for their services (Vincent et al. 2018). Self-organization can be promoted by making space for proposals on future activities, moving out of the tendency to just give updates and opinions. One method to share leadership of the CoP is for each member to do a deep dive into their policy area and invite input for shared learning and strategy exchange. Another method is for different members to showcase the practices they use to inform and make policy and planning decisions.

Ultimately, there needs to be a willingness to adapt methodology and activities to reflect and respond to emerging needs and urgent matters that cannot be anticipated. Many CoPs have failed or fallen apart if they depend too much on key facilitative figures who then move or change their role. Therefore, distributed, shared or rotating leadership is recommended. Finally, some of the activities should also be socially enriching relationships build and endure, consider eliciting proposals for enjoyable activities such as cooking workshops and excursions.

Knowledge brokering

Knowledge brokering is a dynamic and iterative process centred on facilitating the exchange, co-creation, and application of knowledge among diverse stakeholders (Al Busaidy et al., 2023). It is a skilful means of translating knowledge and is a primary activity that enables policy learning. To do so effectively requires an understanding of the learning needs and preferred forms of knowledge for each policymaker and planner. Knowing what evidence they prefer to formulate and advocate for policy change is key. Usually, a mixture of knowledges enables a system transformation, such as high quality emotive narratives, statistical evidence and a civil society campaign to support a policy proposal. Careful knowledge brokerage and meaningful learning can be a way to mobilise knowledge for evidence-based advocacy. It is, therefore, important to be selective on what knowledge to share opting for high quality alignment over high quantity summaries.

At the same time, it is important to not forget or marginalise the knowledge, challenges and potential knowledge requests of the RLI teams. This is particularly the case of those who are most affected by the dominant food system, including participant who experience(d) food insecurity and systemic disadvantages (vulnerabilities). The CoP can be a platform to amplify their lived experience and knowledge in policy circles in a non-extractive manner. It is important to gain consent when translating knowledge from a RLI work group to a policymaking CoP and opportunities should be made for self-representation if wished for.

From knowledge exchange to policy action

Most CoPs do not go further than exchanging knowledge, skills and approaches in relation to their shared interests and practices. They provide an arena to span and bridge boundaries between organisations and disciplines which can result in knowledge that is more transversal and valuable to different stakeholders. It is much more comfortable and easier to give updates, adopt systems thinking and discuss on strategies than to commit to formulating and recommending policy and planning actions.

Unfortunately, there is not a recipe for transitioning from knowledge exchange to policy actions. We know that the building of trust and empathy toward each person's position within larger institutional structures is important. We can be aware of policy cycles and opportunities and attend to openings for civil society and university input. A sense of care and safety enables policymakers and planners to disclose what they can and cannot do as well as hard-to-access information and contacts.

Another strategy can be to temporarily shift the focus towards proposing actions that would mobilise the full potential of policy-practice-research partnerships in the future (Carroll & Crawford 2024). This can be a means to animate future funding and collaborative projects that could include more RLLs, strengthen integrated policy-making processes and embed the CoP more fully into the official workload of policy and planners across departments and sectors. Practicing collaborative, reflexive and adaptive governance and/or seeing the results of this participatory and co-creative approach is also likely to animate a desire to be more involved and committed in the future.

"How do we sustain relationships beyond projects, and enable new projects to come about? It's about bridging between projects but also creating opportunity for new opportunities to come about" (Carroll & Crawford 2024: 7)

4.6 RESOURCES & REFERENCES

Resources

A **playbook to leverage the power of CoPs** from Casel particularly for state policy makers who advance social and emotional learning. Supporting CoP leaders with six steps for building a high quality CoP. <https://casel.org/playbook-community-of-practice/?view=true>

1. Define purpose and objectives
2. Determine scope and sequence, logistics, and resources
3. Recruitment of community of practice members
4. Design agendas for CoP convenings
5. Implement a continuous improvement process
6. Communicate key learnings **and action points**

A CoP **Co-creation Toolkit** from Act on Gender. An accessible compilation of **participatory methods and tools** useful for CoPs to successfully operate and self-develop. <https://lac.act-on-gender.eu/tools/toolkits>

A CoP **Co-creation Toolkit** from University of Glasgow, Organisational Development. **A five stage process** with a great repository of links to **virtual collaboration tools** and further resources. <https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/humanresources/organisationaldevelopment/staffnetworksandcommunities/uofgcommunitiesofpracticetoolkit/whatarecopshowdotheywork/>

A CoP Toolkit from UC Davis Health, School of Medicine. A clear introduction to CoPs with 15 steps to create a CoP with **sample agendas** and **a sample timeline**. https://health.ucdavis.edu/workforce-diversity/What_We_Do/Communities-of-Practice/COPToolkit.html

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4.7 APPENDIX: MYTHS ABOUT COPS

Source: Wenger-Trayner 2015

The diversity of types of communities across different sectors has shown that there is no “one-recipe-fits-all”, despite some of the claims that are made about them. Here are some of the assertions or “myths” that have won some acclaim, in part due to the interpretation of early theoretical writing about them.

Communities of practice are always self-organizing

False. Some communities do self-organize and are very effective. But most communities need some cultivation to be sure that members get high value for their time.

There are no leaders in a true community of practice

Mostly false. In many communities of practice decisions need to be taken, conditions need to be put in place, strategic conversations need to be had. Not all members see value in being involved in these processes. Whether you call them leaders, co-ordinators, or stewards, someone needs to do it – and it is as well to recognize them for the role they play.

True communities of practice are informal

False. There are many informal communities of practice, and there are many formal ones too. The more intentionally they are used for developing the strategic capability of an organization or a cause, the more likely they are to have to go through some formal process to be recognized as such.

The role of a community of practice is to share existing knowledge

Partially true. The experience people have to share is clearly important. But communities of practice also innovate and solve problems. They invent new practices, create new knowledge, define new territory, and develop a collective and strategic voice.

It is too difficult to measure the impact of communities of practice

Mostly false. It may be difficult to attribute with 100% certainty the activities of a community of practice to a particular outcome. You can, however, build a good case using quantitative and qualitative data to measure different types of value created by the community and trace how members are changing their practice and improving performance as a result.

Good facilitation is all it takes to get members to participate

False. Artful facilitation is very important. But there are many other reasons why people may not participate. The domain must be relevant and a priority to members. The value of participation usually needs to be recognized by the organization otherwise members will not bother. Members need to see results of their participation and have a sense that they are getting something out of it. Good facilitation can help to make this visible, but is not the main reason why people participate.

Communities of practice are harmonious places

Maybe. But if they are totally conflict free, you should be concerned that groupthink may be settling in or voices are being silenced. More important, and usually quite difficult to achieve, is that differences are discussable and that they contribute to the learning.

There is a technology that is best for communities of practice

False. There may be, but we haven't found it yet. The online universe is cluttered with spaces that nobody uses. It's also full of sites that are called a community of practice even if no one is there! A tool or technology is as good as it is useful to the people who use it. And a forum is simply a forum until it becomes occupied by a community of practice.

Communities of practice are the solution to everything!

False. Communities of practice don't substitute teams or networks or other joint enterprises. Each has its own place in the overall ecology of the learning system. In recent developments of the theory, we talk about landscapes of practice, and of creating different types of social learning spaces that open up new opportunities for developing learning capability.

5. CO-ORGANIZE A GOVERNANCE EVENT

The guidelines for a governance event clarify core requirements and offer communicational and organisational guidance for

“FPNs to convene a one-day LL event on collaborative and adaptive governance and integrated policy-making for all relevant policy-makers in each of the cities and towns of the city-region, including those of relevant private parties and institutions (school boards and hospitals etc.)”
(Task 3.3, FoodCLIC Description of Action).

These guidelines couple with the guidelines for ‘setting up & running a Community of Practice (CoP) for policy-makers’ especially because part of the governance event is intended as an opportunity to set up or kick-off the establishing of a CoP for policy-makers. Both of these guidelines connect with and are part of the larger set of guidelines for co-creating RLIs. They are vital spaces to increase engagement in the governance of the RLIs during their implementation and to foster supportive policy and planning actions that can strengthen and scale RLIs.

5.1 WHY CONVENE A GOVERNANCE EVENT?

The convening of a governance event *with* FPN organizers is a key strategy for the LLs of real-life interventions (RLIs) to become more effectively embedded within the networks. Not only, can it be an opportunity to strengthen pre-existing connections between network leaders, it is also an opportunity to attract new collaborators, particularly policy-makers, who may have been waiting for something more substantial to emerge before actively supporting RLI implementation.

The governance event is envisioned as a moment to communicate and celebrate the transformation of vision and strategy into the implementation of co-designed RLIs. It is also an important moment to clarify, conceptually and practically, the governance of RLIs and how they can inform and strengthen efforts towards integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning.

This section justifies the three governance approaches that FoodCLIC combines as a way to nourish systemic relationships and transversal knowledges across scales, governmental levels and sectors. Such relationships and knowledges support the refinement of transformative city-region food strategies and their translation into concrete policy and planning actions.

Why collaborative, reflexive and adaptive governance?

The governance event is an opportunity to communicate the governance approaches of the LL of RLIs to policy-makers and invite their participation by accompanying a relevant RLI workgroup and joining a Community of Practice (CoP) for policy makers. The information in this section is meant to be a resource to clearly communicate how we practically apply three governance approaches for added values.

FoodCLIC integrates collaborative, reflexive and adaptive governance approaches to appropriately respond to highly complex and problematic food systems whose current governance is fragmented. All of these approaches correspond with participatory policy-making and relational learning.

There are many governance approaches so why prioritise these three?

Figure 26: Reflexive governance bridges collaborative and adaptive governance

Collaborative governance gets things going, we understand how to improve decision-making and strategic actions by working together across silos and building experiential knowledge. *Reflexive governance* makes space for understanding a plurality of power positions, perspectives and value priorities that shape decision-making. It builds sufficient empathy and trust for systemic integration and innovation to occur. By organizing reflections around experiences and outcomes of collaboration a bridge is made for adaptations (see figure 26). Finally, *adaptive governance* prioritises regular feedback across levels, scales, spheres and sectors of a (food) system to improve decision-making and adjust actions to changing contexts and new learnings.

For more information and conceptual depth on these three forms of governance you can make use of the one-pager in the appendix (section 5.5) of these guidelines.

Figure 27: Application of governance approaches in LL contexts with action-research spiral

Figure 27 illustrates how the three governance approaches are applied in a FoodCLIC's LLs. The implementation of the RLIs is structured into four action-learning cycles of act-observe-reflect-(re)plan. Different moments of the cycle require different governance practices.

Practically, collaborative governance focuses on the implementation of the RLIs. Each RLI workgroup coordinates and co-organises actions and (sub)activities of their RLI. The **RLI action plan** and other collaboration agreements, such as memorandums of understanding, are vital accountability mechanisms to decide and commit to collaborative roles and responsibilities.

Practically, reflexive governance focuses on the four reflexive learning sessions. In these sessions RLI collaborators reflect on their observations and monitor the impacts of RLI actions/activities on RLI objectives. Deliberative space is made to reflect on relationships, obstacles/barriers in achieving ambitions, and the making of action-oriented learning questions. A **DLA template**, or alternative, tracks reflexive learning across the cycles.

Practically, adaptive governance focuses on the latter half of the RLI reflexive learning sessions where new learnings and insights generate adjustments to RLI action plans. Not only are learning questions renewed, but also RLI action plans. Space is made for agile and strategic responses to intermediate monitoring results and significant feedback such as significant changes in contexts, needs, priorities and opportunities.

In a nutshell, the FoodCLIC living labs collaborate via RLIs, reflect in four action-learning cycles and adapt RLI action plans after each reflexive learning session.

Pathways to integrated policy-making & food-sensitive planning

There are many pathways to integrated policy-making and food-sensitive planning. The FoodCLIC collaboration offers one pathway that prioritises democratic multi-stakeholder governance via collaboration, reflective monitoring and adaptation of real-life interventions. Such practices build integral relationships of trust and empowerment across a city-region food system to learn and advance evidence-based and context-appropriate strategies.

Similar pathways have been proved to be effective in pioneering effective and integrated food policies that succeeded in reducing health inequalities and increasing access to healthier foods. Take for example, the inspiring cases of Leeds and Amsterdam who, according to BBC (2024), are “two of the only places in the world to have cut rates of childhood obesity” which you can learn about in [an inspiring podcast here](#).

This section provides some educational and communicational resources relating to integrated food policy-making and food-sensitive planning. A guiding exploratory question is: how can FoodCLIC’s LLs and the FPN’s CoP for policymakers catalyse such progressive changes in policy and planning.

Integrated food policy-making

FoodCLIC’s DoA offers a definition for an evidence-based integrated food policy:

*A **food policy** includes a problem statement, a set of objectives and a concrete course of action (implementation action plan), using policy instruments (e.g., laws and (tax) regulations, (urban) land-use planning, investments and subsidy schemes, communication strategies, covenants, etc.) over time with a specified resource allocation.*

***Integrated food policies** work along all four pillars of the project’s CLIC framework to: (i) realize sustainability co-benefits; (ii) establish linkages between urban and rural areas; (iii) include all relevant food system stakeholders; and (iv) build connections between food and other policy domains.*

*An **evidence-based policy** builds on both state-of-the-art scientific knowledge and experiential knowledge.*

Figure 28: CLIC pillars as key components/indicators of integrated food policies

FoodCLIC theorises four desirable outputs of an integrated food policy. These are sustainability **co-benefits** between economic, environmental and social objectives; rural-urban **linkages**, **inclusion** of all stakeholders and their knowledges; and **connectivities** between food and other policies, sectors and systems. This is visualised in the figure 28.

The report on “facilitators of and barriers to the development and implementation of evidence-based and integrated food policies and planning frameworks” (Deliverable 2.1) draws on academic and grey literature to highlight key areas for municipal decision-makers to develop and implement integrated food policies that include the CLIC dimensions. Four recommendations are made, including (1) fostering a collective commitment, (2) building on existing strengths and resources, (3) promoting inclusive, diverse, just and relevant representation, and (4) governance integration.

1. **Fostering collective commitment:** The creation of an inclusive policy context is fundamental for fostering collective commitment. For this, stakeholders should develop a common definition of the problem they want to tackle, a shared vision of the desirable urban food system and the pathway to achieve it. Reflexive cycles throughout this process are essential to ensure participant’s voices and opinions are heard and deliberated, and that the ensuing outcomes are embedded within policy.
2. **Building on existing strengths and resources:** At the start of formulating an integrated food policy, it is recommended to assess the local context to identify relevant strengths, resources and policy initiatives that could be mobilised and leveraged around food. This allows creating synergies between different local resources and valuing local experiences and knowledge to create an enabling and supportive environment for integrated food policies.
3. **Promoting inclusive, diverse, just and relevant representation:** Participation in policy formulation should include the people who are intended to receive the benefits of the policy, as well as powerful stakeholders in supportive roles. The details of how policy is formulated

and expressed also affects their inclusivity and implementation. For that, carefully choosing the terminology is of highly importance.

4. **Governance integration:** Urban food policies benefit from policy engagement and integration at both horizontal (i.e., between municipal governments) and vertical (from civil society to municipal to state, national and international levels) levels. Novel governance mechanisms such as the appointment of a food policy officer can be helpful. The CLIC framework can also provide strategies to integrate food policies across and within governance levels that complement each other in achieving integrated policy outcomes.

Other key pathways to achieving integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks exist and in the remainder of this section we highlight two relevant ones, and their connection to the CLIC framework. Parsons (2010) departs from the contents of an integrated food policy and distributes awareness to three strategies or types of making integrated food policies (see figure 29). One strategy is to 'bring policies together' by creating a new plan or strategy that brings all/as-many-as-possible aspects of policy related to food together in an overarching cross-government project. A second is ensuring food is reflected in other relevant policy areas and departments, such as social welfare, urban planning, public health etc. A third is to use policy measures as leverage points to address multiple food system goals together. Becoming more aware of policy and planning cycles within the timeframe of the FoodCLIC should provide more context-sensitive openings to leverage the momentum of the FPN and the results of relevant RLIs into different types of integrated policy-making.

Types of Integrated Food Policy

Figure 29: Types of integrated food policy (Parsons 2019)

Food sensitive-planning

FoodCLIC's DoA offers a definition for a food-sensitive planning framework:

A framework that organizes the physical, material or spatial elements of an (urban) area and comprises:

- (i) a framework plan, also called a "strategic plan" or "vision plan," which articulates a clear vision for (urban) planning, including food priorities, and has a long-term horizon intended to articulate the big picture ideas, goals, and principles;*
- (ii) planning process, which establishes a clear process and mechanisms to support the interactions of public, private, and community sectors during the development and implementation of the plan, including questions around food; and*
- (iii) planning regulations, which form the legal regime that frame the planning process (i.e., zoning laws and land-use plans)*

While FoodCLIC defines the ambitions, Ilieva (2016) provides a potentially useful heuristic or general pathway where the food system becomes a stable and integral part of urban policy and planning culture. Figure 30 visualises the pathway in four progressive stages with increasing integration over time. In the predevelopment phase the food system is a stranger to the planning field, in the take-off phase the food system becomes part of the research agenda with some episodes practice. The 'acceleration' phase entails increased institutionalisation until the stabilisation phase where food system planning is equal to established planning fields, such as land-use, public health, housing and transportation.

Figure 30: Phases of transition towards a food-sensitive urban policy and planning (Ilieva 2016: 10)

It can be a valuable exercise for policy-makers and planners to map the degree of food system integration into their own planning and policy domains as a starting point from which to identify context-appropriate strategies for food system transformation. For example, if food system planning is still in the predevelopment phase, then sharing great practices and capacity-building via direct participation in RLIs make sense as effective strategies.

A final strategy towards engaging stakeholders to connect LLs with food sensitive planning is to focus on the senses. Haysom et al. (2020) build on existing theory and practice to identify seven senses that guide food-sensitive planning which are summarised in figure 31. How can the collaborate-reflect-adapt approach to LL governance enhance the senses? Which RLIs develop which senses?

Figure 31: Seven senses guiding food-sensitive planning (Haysom et al. 2020: 72)

5.2 CORE REQUIREMENTS

The core requirements are grouped into three timings; before, during and after the governance event.

Before the governance event takes place:

1. All of the RLIs should have co-designed individual **RLI action plans**
 - Each RLI action plan documents, as a minimum, the preparatory actions of cycle 1 (May to September 2024) and the upcoming implementation actions of cycle 2 (September to March 2025).
 - An [adaptable RLI action plan template](#) with guidance is provided in the “implement and learn from RLIs” guidelines.
2. All of the RLIs should have their own individual **RLI monitoring plans**
 - Each RLI monitoring plan contains the success criteria, i.e. contextual indicators, for each of the activities and actions of a RLI (derived from the RLI action plan). It defines the methods and records actual measurements of contextual indicators, chosen/consented to by the RLI workgroup, to evidence progress/impact of RLI actions
 - An **adaptable RLI monitoring template** will be presented in the next monthly support session and more guidance is provided in the RMDE framework
3. By the time the governance event takes place, at least half of the RLI work groups have completed a reflexive learning session with the results recorded in a standardised **reflexive learning report/tracker**
 - The results of a reflexive learning session include, reflections between RLI objectives and actions, learning questions and new activities to overcome barriers/challenges for the next action-learning cycle
 - We highly recommend the use of the DLA method and have provided an [adaptable DLA reporting template](#) with guidance in the “implement and learn from RLIs” guidelines.
4. The governance event is prepared and co-organised with the LL coordinator(s), LL researcher(s) and FPN leaders/organisers who convene the governance event

During the governance event

1. The governance event contains at least two parts with at least 2.5 hours per part to qualify as a “one-day governance event” (DoA). The two parts can be organised on different days with the participation of as many relevant policy-makers as possible.
2. The first part builds understanding how the collaborative, reflexive and adaptive governance of RLIs is well-suited to build contextualised-evidence and capacities for informing and making integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning
3. The second part kicks-off a CoP for policy-makers within or across the convening FPN(s) and includes a practical experience of reflexive governance. Participants reflect on the

results of relevant RLI reflexive learning sessions and decide on their own action-oriented learning questions to guide the agenda for the next CoP meeting.

After the governance event

1. A short and accessible report is made of the governance event, including who participated, and it is shared on the social media channels of the FPN(s).

5.3 KEY OBJECTIVES & COMPONENTS

This section provides guidance on how to organize the convening of a governance event into two parts, each containing its own objectives, associated components and further recommendations. Acknowledging the plurality of trajectories, contexts and capacities of the participating FPNs and LL teams the guidelines are as flexible and open as possible. You are encouraged to adapt the objectives and activities to what makes most strategic sense.

Part 1 – Present RLIs & discuss governance approaches

The recommended objectives and components of the first part of the governance event are:

2. Communicate the collaborative process of FoodCLIC from mapping and visioning to strategizing and co-design of RLI portfolio with individual action plans as well as the presentation of D2.1 on the barriers and facilitators of evidence-based integrated food policies and food sensitive planning frameworks
3. Clarify the LL governance model/structure that combines three governance approaches to test and adapt RLIs to make evidence-based food strategies, integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks
3. Discuss the three governance approaches, including the capacities that they require and their opportunities and challenges for contributing to city-region food system transformations, i.e. integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning rules

Recommendations:

The governance event is an opportunity to officially celebrate or showcase the LL's portfolio of RLIs and the innovative governance approach. It is an opportunity for the expansion of FPN membership and engagement. This requires inviting policy-makers and powerful institutional actors who may be outside your jurisdictions, operating in other towns and municipalities.

Make use of simple visuals and diagrams from these guidelines and make short, concise definitions in your own words to communicate collaborative, reflexive and adaptive governance and how they are practiced in the LLs. You can make use of the appendix: three forms of governance to make your own working definitions. Try to embed the LL governance within the governance structure of the convening FPNs and ongoing policy processes.

Objectives one and two should be limited to 30 minutes of presentation. This could be extended a little, especially if there are multiple presenters, representing different RLI workgroups. Print-off one-page visual summaries on the tables as reminders.

Objective three can be organised into two activities. The first can focus on discussing the challenges and opportunities for these governance approaches contributing to policy and planning change from the perspectives and contexts of the participants. The second activity can focus on the participants self-identifying which approaches they want to practice more and which capacities they want to strengthen. Storytelling or testimonies from policy-makers already participating in RLI and/or governance practices can increase engagement and interest in the activities.

Ask the RLI workgroups who to invite and what form of support or participation they may want if there is interest from participants in the governance event to join their work group. Gain consent in what is communicated about the RLI, i.e. its action plan, contextual indicators, and create opportunities for self-representation.

Part 2 – Experience reflexive governance & kick-off CoP

The recommended objectives and components of the second part of the governance event are:

1. Relevant policy-makers from across the city-region experience reflexive governance by participating in a (meta-)reflexive learning session
2. Policy-makers reflect on relevant learning questions and intermediate monitoring results from RLI work groups before making their own personal learning questions
2. Policy-makers participate in the prospective design or contents of a CoP for policy-makers, including ways of capacity strengthening and exchanging with RLI workgroups
3. Action points are made to officially establish the CoP with a follow-up meeting scheduled

Recommendations:

Make strategic choices on what knowledge to share depending on the number of policy-makers and their interests. For example, if there are many interested in public procurement, then make a table which prioritises a more detailed knowledge share on the RLI learning questions and monitoring results from the RLI workgroup focusing on public procurement. A balance does need to be found between specialising and also making opportunities for interconnections between RLIs and their respective policy areas so that integrated policy-making can occur.

Make use of visuals, insightful quotes and photos (with consent) of the RLI reflexive learning sessions that took place before the governance event. This increases accessibility and engagement in the (meta-)reflexive learning session. A facilitator script is provided in section 3B of the guidelines for 'implementing and learning from RLIs'. What makes this reflexive learning session a 'meta'

session is that policy-makers reflect not only on their position and practice, but also on the reflections, learning questions and results from relevant RLI workgroups (see figure 32).

Figure 32: A visual of the relationships between the RLI workgroups, FPN and CoP

Find a balance between offering a starting structure and stable form, i.e. four CoP (meta-) reflexive learning sessions (every 5-6 months), and between making space for it to be re-designed and have added value for the policy-makers. Share the proposal and ask for feedback. More guidance is available in the guidelines for ‘setting up and running a CoP for policy-makers’, including considerations on how to embed the CoP in the FPN(s) and sustain the CoP beyond FoodCLIC.

The experience of a reflexive learning session is in itself a micro-practice of reflexive governance. Starting with knowledge and strategy exchanges and the strengthening of governance capacity building can be effective starting-point to kick-off a CoP. If policy-makers have more urgent and action-oriented priorities, such as implementing a pre-existing food policy or revising a pre-existing food strategy for healthy, just and sustainable food, then it makes sense to adapt the objectives and design of this part and the CoP itself.

5.4 RESOURCES & REFERENCES

Resources

A **governance toolkit** from Generative-Commons that was developed by Community Land Trust Brussels. Instead of providing ready-made decisional systems or organizational structures the toolkit offers processes and activities “that could lead collectives to investigate their conditions, assess their capacities, envision their future, and **learn about the most appropriate choices in terms of legal and governance structures**”. <https://generative-commons.eu/the-governance-toolkit/>

We identified three main needs and unsolved issues of the collectives and commons initiatives concerning governance:

- *Maintaining the alignment with their mission and values while redefining their future and preparing for growth.*
- *Learning about their rights and responsibilities and exploring and assessing the most appropriate forms of governance.*
- *Dealing with space and with the unavoidable impact it has on governance matters.*

A coaching system called Mirroring, a roleplaying game called Commons and Dragons and an architectural modelling methodology called Space Matters are the tools we developed to respond to these needs while triggering meaningful processes.

A **handbook on capacity-building using living labs** from OPEN Lab, European Commission, with a chapter (5, pp 80-92) on governance models and a LL governance template. https://openlab-project.eu/app/uploads/D1-4_Capacity-Building-Handbook-Mentoring-report-89.pdf

A **collaborative framework for food systems transformation** from One Planet Network, UN environment, with 5 principles of a food systems approach to policymaking and implementation. <https://www.oneplanetnetwork.org/knowledge-centre/resources/collaborative-framework-food-systems-transformation-multi-stakeholder>

A publication on **seven governance criteria for effectively addressing primary challenges for collaborative governance of regional food systems** from JustFoodGov. The report shares key lessons and recommendations for implementation. <https://radishgroup.ca/publication/2022-justfoodgov/>

1. Representing sectoral interests
2. Supporting diversity, inclusion and accessibility
3. Responding to inequities in power
4. Building external relationship

5. Promoting public participation and transparency
6. Fostering opportunities for adequate resourcing
7. Embedding adaptive capacity

An **integrated food policy guide** from Kelly Parsons, City University of London Centre for Food Policy, that proposes three different types of integrated food policy with links to clear and concise policy briefs such as ‘what is integrated food policy and how can it transform food systems?’ and ‘connecting food systems for co-benefits’. <https://www.kellyparsons.co.uk/integrated-food-policy>

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5.5 APPENDIX: THREE FORMS OF GOVERNANCE

Collaborative governance:

FPNs play a convener role in bringing people together across a food system to work collaboratively on projects and provide a forum for policy learning and action (Giddy et al. 2022). Collaborative governance (sometimes called “networked” or “polycentric” governance) bridges separations between conventional jurisdictions, organisational lines, public-private-community spheres and other boundaries to co-create and sustain public/common goods, i.e. healthy, affordable and sustainable food for all.

Collaborative governance usually involves selective and strategic inclusion of stakeholders (Ansell et al. 2020) and struggles to ensure equal access in decision-making of the process, especially when there are power imbalances between stakeholders (Ansell & Gash 2008). Constructive dialogue is prioritised as a relationship building strategy to align stakeholder perspectives and interests. Collaborative governance has been most effective when participants apply democratic and accountability mechanisms (such as action plans), acknowledge their inter-dependence and reach a common understanding on what can be achieved together (Oñederra-Aramendi et al. 2023).

Reflexive governance:

Reflexive governance “focuses on the central role of social learning as a mode of governance, fostering adaptation and collaboration between stakeholders... as well as collective cognition and social capital formation, both necessary for collective action”. It prioritises inclusive dialogue that fosters greater recognition and respect for multiple perspectives, framings, and experiences of complex problems (Sonnino & Spayde 2014). Through regular reflexive deliberations and negotiations, it becomes possible to reach broadly supported and integrated strategies and action plans.

Well organised and carefully structured reflections enable the co-production of holistic and plural knowledges with capacity to address complex problems, such as food insecurity and health inequalities (Oñederra-Aramendi et al. 2023). In relation to achieving just food-system transitions, reflexive governance seeks to understand variation in food movements and networks, i.e. different objectives and starting points, as well as their limits and the ways their differences can complement (Huttunen et al. 2022: 509).

Adaptive governance:

Adaptive governance responds to the failure of “command and control” management by supporting people and institutions to organise in a learn-by-doing way (Ollivier et al. 2018). Deliberate spaces and moments are made to adjust decisions and actions in light of evidence and lessons learned from ongoing interactions between peoples, environments and systems (Olsson et al. 2014). There is a prioritisation towards building capacities to foster resilience, flexibility and responsivity to systemic uncertainty and complexity (Folke et al. 2005).

Adaptive governance aims to reconcile asymmetric interactions across multiple scales and levels via organised feedback and making of transversal knowledge and bridge-building interactions (Pereira & Ruysenaar (2012). Decentralised governance mechanisms are preferred to move governance towards healthier and networked relations of inter-dependence (ibid, Oñederra-Aramendi et al. 2023).

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